

REPORT ON RESEARCH AND DEVELOPMENT OF ENERGY TECHNOLOGIES

**EDITED BY
IUPAP WORKING GROUP ON ENERGY**

OCTOBER 6, 2004

SUMMARY

SUMMARY	2
I - PREFACE	3
II – EXECUTIVE SUMMARY	5
<i>II-1 Renewable Energy</i>	6
<i>II-2 Hydrogen and Fuel Cells</i>	7
<i>II-3 Fossil Energy</i>	7
<i>II-4 Nuclear Fission Energy</i>	8
<i>II-5 Nuclear Fusion Energy</i>	8
<i>II-6 Conclusions - Outlook</i>	8
III-REPORT	9
<i>III-1.Introduction</i>	9
<i>III-2 Conclusions on the energy situation from reports in different selected countries and from global projections</i>	12
<i>III-3 Summaries of R & D on energy technology reports from experts</i>	16
3.1 Fossil fuels	16
3.1.1.Fossil fuel fired power plants including CO ₂ sequestration and storage.....	16
3.1.2.Fossil fuels fired high temperature fuel cells	17
3.1.3.Liquid fuels in the transportation sector: conversion of natural gas to methanol	18
3.1.4.Non conventional resources of fossil fuels: methane hydrates in sediments of continental sea shelves.....	18
3.2 Nuclear fission energy	18
3.3 Renewable energy	19
3.3.1. “Solar” electric energy via photovoltaics (PV).....	22
3.3.2.Storage of electric energy	22
3.3.3.Solar thermal power plants, STPP	22
3.3.4.Wind power plants	23
3.3.5.Hydro Power.....	23
3.3.6.Biofuels	23
3.3.7.Geothermal energy.....	24
3.4 Hydrogen	24
3.5 Low temperature fuel cells.....	24
3.6 Nuclear fusion energy	25
IV-CONCLUSIONS – OUTLOOK	27
V- ANNEX A: LIST OF EXPERT REPORTS ON R & D OF SPECIAL ENERGY TECHNOLOGIES	28
VI-ANNEX B: LIST OF COUNTRY REPORTS ON THEIR SPECIAL ENERGY SITUATION	34
VIII-USEFUL ABBREVIATIONS AND DEFINITIONS	36

I – PREFACE

The general assembly of IUPAP, in Berlin in October 2002, formed a Working Group on Energy, to which it gave the task to provide:

a survey of Research and Development (R & D) of Energy Technologies toward the future provision of any kind of secondary energy* demanded:

- electric energy
- fuels in transportation sector
- high and low temperature heat

Obviously they must be all in sufficient amounts, environmentally safe and at sufficiently low cost by making best use of any kind of primary energy including

- fossil fuels (oil, gas, coal)
- nuclear fission energy (produced in a nuclear reactor by dividing the nucleus of an atom
- nuclear fusion energy (produced by the fusion of two atomic nuclei)
- renewable energy

This survey of R & D of Energy Technologies should help to sharpen the interest

- of scientists, especially physicists, in universities, in research institutions, in industry to devote their further work to this challenging field of science
- of media people to inform the public with sufficient completeness on this subject of vital importance
- of policy makers on the attractive potential for future ample business opportunities in the field of energy technologies as well as in many other fields.

To produce this report

- we invited scientific experts of different countries to provide short surveys of many different energy technologies describing the present status as well as the future R & D required to further develop the corresponding technology for proper ample use in the future
- we have further collected reports on the special energy situation in different countries around the globe concerning
 - . the present demand on energy
 - . the possible future demand on energy together with ideas how this demand can be met
 - . the availability of different kinds of primary energy to provide any kind of secondary energy demanded
 - . the needs of further R & D on future energy technologies

We ourselves have briefly summarized the manifold energy technologies and the collected reports on the energy situation in different countries. Furthermore we have drawn conclusions on the further need of R & D of energy technologies towards future provision of energy in sufficient amount, environmentally safe and at sufficient low cost, keeping in mind that availability of energy is a limiting factor to further economic development especially in many fast developing countries around the globe.

* Examples of secondary energy: electricity, heat, gasoline.

We would like to thank the scientific experts for their most informative contribution on special energy technologies and Herve Nifenecker and T. Alfstad for their country reports on the energy situation in France respectively and in South Africa.

To read more easily this report, some units and definitions are given on page 36..

Prof. Klaus Heinloth, Chair, Bonn University
heinloth@physik.uni-bonn.de

Prof. Burton Richter, IUPAP Representative,
Stanford University brichter@slac.stanford.edu

Prof. Y. Nagai, Osaka University
nagai@rcnp.osaka-u.ac.jp

Prof. Felix Yndurain, Universidad Autonoma de Madrid
felix.yndurain@uam.es

Prof. Jon Samseth, Norwegian Physical Society
jon.samseth@sintef.no

Prof. Rogerio Cerqueira Leite, Campinas University
cerqueiraleite@uol.com.br

Prof. John Ahearne, Duke University
ahearne@sigmaxi.org

Prof. Yuping Huo, Chinese Academy of Sciences
huoyp@zzu.edu.cn

Prof. P. K. Kaw, Institute for Plasma Research-India
kaw@ipr.res.in

Prof. O. N. Favorskyi, Russian Academy of Sciences
ptped@ipsun.ras.ru

II – EXECUTIVE SUMMARY

The world population of about six billion humans (at present) is expected to culminate to about nine billion humans around the middle of this century, this further increase mainly due to developing countries with fast rising populations and fast economic development as well like e.g. China, India and Brazil. In the same period the global Gross Domestic Product (GDP) is expected to further rise by at least about a factor 2 to 3, an appreciable fraction of it by fast developing countries like mentioned. With hopefully further rising energy efficiency - like in the past - to be achieved in already industrialized countries as well as especially in developing countries the further increase of the global demand on energy may be limited to about a factor 1.5 to 2.

To achieve this required provision of energy calls for [physics achievements in the future](#) by proper R & D of energy technologies

- to further provide sufficient secondary energy (electric energy, fuels in transportation sector, high and low temperature heat) with hopefully further appreciable increase of the energy efficiency allowing the development necessary to improve the life of people around the globe, especially in countries with further strong population growth, e.g. China and India
- by proper use of available primary energy sources (fossil fuels ,nuclear fission, renewable energy, nuclear fusion)
 - . in an environmentally safe way reducing, respectively avoiding risks of nuclear energy as well as reducing, limiting risks and dangers of climate change
 - . adaptable to possible changing environmental conditions not to be foreseen now
 - . and last but not least at sufficiently low cost.

Presently the main source of commercial primary energy (on global average about 85 %) are the fossil fuels, coal, crude oil and natural gas.

At the present status of energy technologies, the future provision of energy from non-fossil energy sources is more or less rather limited,

- either because of limited availability (e.g. hydro power)
- and/or because of relatively high investment cost (e.g. nuclear fission power)
- or because of very high investment costs and missing availability of energy storage (e.g. wind power and photovoltaics)

Therefore fossil fuels are expected to continue to be the dominant source of primary energy at least within the next decades despite the danger of climate change.

To reconcile both confronting necessities (providing sufficient energy and reducing further emission of carbon dioxide from burning of fossil fuels) requires strong efforts on both

- R & D on non fossil energy technologies
 - . nuclear fission
 - . nuclear fusion
 - . renewable energy
- to gradually substitute the further use of fossil fuels within some to many decades

- R & D on clean fossil energy technologies
 - . increasing the efficiency of power plants
 - . including CO₂ sequestration and depositionto allow fossil fuels to still be the major source of primary energy within the next decades.

This is an area where a very large effort has to be made. One has to be pragmatic: some countries such as China and India have very large populations and very large reserves of coal and it is clear that they will continue to use it. So, it is absolutely necessary to increase the efficiency of power plants including CO₂ sequestration and deposition, to allow fossil fuels to still be the major source of primary energy within the next decades.

It is an important and exciting task of physics (and other disciplines) concerning R & D on energy technologies, to discover and prepare new ways based on brilliant ideas, making use of computational physics, nano sciences and nano technologies to provide any secondary energy demanded from any kind of primary energy.

A large variety of energy technologies can be tackled by challenging R & D covering nearly any branch of modern physics, never restricted to one branch alone, always basic physics and applied physics linked together inseparably. This should include strong collaborations with other disciplines like chemistry, biology, computer and material science.

II-1 Renewable Energy

Further R & D on “solar” electric energy via photovoltaics (PV) is pursued on well established paths as well as on completely new roads to achieve much higher efficiencies and this at much lower cost.

Intimately connected to solar electric energy via PV is the required storage of electric energy

- either directly in rechargeable batteries hoping to finally achieve much higher storage densities and this at much lower cost than at present
- or indirectly e.g. via producing and storing hydrogen to be later used in fuel cells to produce electric energy

A further option of solar electric energy is the solar thermal power plant - restricted to low latitude arid regions with high insolation - especially with possible cheap storage of high temperature heat to provide electric power continuously.

Major further R & D on wind power is concentrated on the development of wind rotor generator units with some MW max. electric power to be installed “offshore” in shallow ocean regions to extend the intervals of providing electric power from typically up to about 20 percent of availability in time (typical for on shore and inland wind rotor installations) to about 30 to 40 percent.

Concerning hydro power

- the technologies of high pressure reservoir and low pressure river power plants are well established
- the technology of tidal power plants is available in principle and has been investigated comprehensively. But its further realization, beyond the existing 240 MW tidal power plant at the Rance estuary in France, has been barred mainly by the rather high expenses to be expected.
- the technologies of ocean wave and ocean current power conversion still require extensive R & D both for large power facilities to be installed in the open ocean as well as for small power facilities to be installed in shallow coastal areas.

To provide [biofuel from biomass](#) may be rather promising for countries with proper large areas of land suitable for agricultural energy crops at present like e.g. Brazil. On a global scale the bottle neck for providing a large fraction of the demand on liquid fuels for the transportation sector is the limited availability of sufficient areas for agricultural land to provide sufficient amounts of food for a world population, expected to rise from about 6 to at least about 9 billion humans.

II-2 Hydrogen and Fuel Cells

[Hydrogen](#) is a secondary energy carrier to possibly be provided from any type of primary energy respectively of secondary energy like electric energy or high temperature heat. For future provision of hydrogen by large amounts, rather challenging R & D along different new ways is required and, is partially already ongoing, e.g.

- photo electrolysis (by special PV cells)
- solar thermal \
- photo chemical - catalytic
- photo biological - water splitting
- thermo chemical /

As an [alternative](#) to the difficult handling of hydrogen, R & D towards converting hydrogen directly at the location of its production via synthesis with CO₂ extracted from the atmosphere to a [proper synfuel](#) like e.g. methanol, may finally lead to avoid the expensive infrastructure of a future hydrogen economy.

Low temperature [fuel cells](#), especially Polymer Electrolyte Membrane Fuel Cells (PEMFC) and Direct Methanol Fuel Cells (DMFC) are regarded as forthcoming future technologies for mobile provision of electric power especially on board of fuel cell electric motor vehicles.

Further challenging, rather imaginative R & D is required to overcome the many difficulties at present, last not least to reduce the cost of fuel cells by up to 2 orders of magnitude to become competitive with present vehicle propulsion by internal combustion engines.

II-3 Fossil Energy

Challenging R & D is required to do the splits between:

- limiting the further increase of the CO₂ content of the atmosphere

- and making innovative use of conventional and non conventional resources of fossil fuels and especially to do the splits between
- increasing the efficiency of fossil fuel fired power plants
- and implementing innovative CO₂ sequestration and deposition.

II-4 Nuclear Fission Energy

R & D is aiming towards

- evolutionary improvements of nuclear power plants to be built in the near future by further decrease of the of the risk of a large accident of Light Water Reactors and by avoiding the risk of a large accident completely by making use of inherently safe High Temperature Reactors
- revolutionary improvements of nuclear power plants to become available after many decades, perhaps heading finally for nearly closed fuel cycles via breeding and reprocessing of fuel and for reducing the radioactive waste largely by transmutation to shorten the lifetime of radioactive waste, if these technologies can become economic.

II-5 Nuclear Fusion Energy

Further necessary R & D for at least some more decades towards finally a technically as well as economically acceptable solution of fusion power plants is pursued at present with rather different options of fusion technologies

- magnetic confinement of the fusion plasma via TOKAMAK (next step: ITER) and STELLARATOR magnet configurations
- inertial confinement of the fusion plasma via LASER generated x-rays, electric pulse generated x-rays and heavy ion beams

until hopefully at least one of these options or even a further option like e.g. muon catalytic fusion leads to an acceptable solution.

II-6 Conclusions - Outlook

To be kept in mind: fossil fuels will continue to be the dominant source of primary energy at least within the next few decades. It will take some to many decades to improve the use of other sources of primary energy like e.g. nuclear fission and renewable energy to be able to play a much more important role to satisfy our demand on energy than nowadays. This is intimately linked to the ability to cut cost of providing energy from nuclear and especially from renewable energy appreciably, and -concerning the increased use of renewable energy with strongly intermittent availability- to find new ways to store energy, especially electric energy efficiently and cost effectively.

Nuclear fusion energy may become an option only in the far more distant future of many decades. Therefore R & D on clean fossil fuel technologies with highest possible efficiencies and including CO₂ sequestration and storage respectively use is of utmost importance.

III-REPORT

III-1 Introduction

The development of early mankind for some million years was extremely slow leading to a rise of the world population to a few million humans at the end of the last glacial period about 13,000 years ago [BRO].

Since the onset of the present interglacial warm period mankind was able for the first time to settle down, to provide increasingly more food by agriculture and cattle breeding, this because of the warm climate with its unusual stability in average temperature. During the 13,000 years up till about 300 years ago, the world population rose from a few million to about 600 million humans.

With the onset of the industrialization, since 300 to 200 years ago, the world population rose extremely fast from 600 million to already more than 6,000 million humans at present.

The industrialization has been made possible by outstanding achievements of technology and science, especially physics, for example:

- steam engine by J. Watt (1769)
- electric generator and motor by W. v. Siemens (1866)
- coal fired power plants including an extended electric grid by H. Stinnes (1898)
- ICE motor car by C. + B. Benz (1888) for everybody by H. Ford (1903)
- electric battery by A. Volta (1798)
- electromagnetism by J. C. Maxwell (1861)
- electric light bulb by T. Edison (1879)
- electromagnetic waves by H. Hertz (1887)
- electron by J. J. Thomson (1892)
- transistor by J. Bardeen, W. H. Brattain, W. Shockley (1948)
- fast rising provision of food:
 - . artificial fertilizer by F. Haber (1909)
 - . high yield corn and wheat by N. E. Borlaug (1960).

Many of these and many more achievements led to a multiplication of man power by artificial power, making rapidly rising use of fossil fuels

- coal since about 1700
- crude oil since about 1900
- natural gas since about 1950

These have been the main sources of energy because of their ample and steady, non fluctuating availability and -last not least- their relatively low cost compared to availability and cost of renewable energy used so far.

Within the last 100 years the global annual demand on primary energy rose from about 1 billion tons of coal equivalent (1BtCE) to about 14 billion at present, of which

78 percent is from fossil fuels

6 percent is from nuclear energy

6 percent is from commercial renewable energy

10 percent is from non commercial renewably energy.

Now, if we have a look into the future:

the further rising world population is expected to culminate with about 9,000 million humans around mid of this century. At present nearly 2/3 of the total demand on energy is by industrialized countries with about 1/4 of the world population. Since many more countries, especially those with already high and still fast rising populations like e.g. China, India and Brazil exhibit fast rising economic development, the future global demand on energy is expected to rise by at least 50 percent within the next several decades.

The further availability (from today's knowledge) of fossil fuels is restricted at present rates of consumption

- conventional crude oil to about 4 more decades
- conventional natural gas to about 7 more decades
- conventional coal to a few hundred years.

Furthermore, it is of utmost importance to address climate change caused by climate warming induced by the exuberant burning of fossil fuels [IPCC]: the direct release of heat by burning fossil fuels - globally only less than 0.01 percent of global warming by sunlight - is negligible. Not negligible, but highly dangerous is the increase of greenhouse warming due to the increase of the content of the atmosphere on carbon dioxide: when burning fossil fuels about half of the carbon dioxide released remains in the atmosphere for at least some hundred years. Since burning fossil fuels as the main source of energy required by mankind, the carbon dioxide content of the atmosphere has been increased by about 1/3, from 0.28 per mille of volume about 200 years ago to 0.37 per mille at present. Mainly this rise has led to an additional greenhouse warming on global average by about 1 percent compared to insolation of light, which has already caused a rise of the temperature on global average by close to 1 degree Celsius.

With still further rising consumption of fossil fuels with unrestricted release of carbon dioxide during the next decades we have to expect a further rise of the temperature by some more degrees. This rise of temperature poses the risk of climate changes most dangerous to mankind and to nature in many to most regions around the globe:

For instance:

- the unusual stability of the global mean temperature, allowing agriculture and cattle breeding to provide sufficient food for at present 6 billion humans, may suddenly change to a climate with rapid fluctuations of the mean temperature, similar to that of the preceding interglacial warm period between 130,000 to 115,000 years ago.
- the north polar ice cap may melt at least partially, leading to at least a strong reduction of the intensity of the gulf current rather suddenly –which transfers enough heat mainly from the equatorial Caribbean region to western and northern Europe, to additionally heat these regions by several degrees Celsius. This would lead to a decrease of the average temperature in Europe by several degrees, significantly impacting agriculture and forestry.
- In the case of a melting of the west Antarctic ice shield –which has happened during the previous interglacial warm period at a temperature on global and long-term average of only about one to a few degrees above the present average temperature on earth– the sea

level would rise by about five meters flooding coastal areas where about one third of the world population is living at present

To fight global warming sufficiently, the further rise of the average temperature has to be limited as much as still possible, certainly to less than a few more degrees. This calls for a strong reduction of the release of carbon dioxide from further burning of fossil fuels on global average to less than ½ of the release at present, to be achieved hopefully within the next few decades.

To achieve this goal calls for [physics achievements in the future](#) by proper R & D of energy technologies

- to further provide sufficient secondary energy (electric energy, fuels in transportation sector, high and low temperature heat) with hopefully further appreciable increase of the energy efficiency allowing the development necessary to improve the life of people around the globe, especially in countries with further strong population growth, e.g. China and India
- by proper use of available primary energy sources (fossil fuels, nuclear fission, renewable energy, nuclear fusion) in an environmentally safe way reducing, respectively avoiding risks of nuclear energy as well as reducing, limiting risks and dangers of climate change. This should be adaptable to possible changing environmental conditions not foreseen now and last but not least at sufficient low cost.

III-2 Conclusions on the energy situation from reports in different selected countries and from global projections

AT PRESENT

the highly industrialized countries of today,

- with about $\frac{1}{4}$ of the world population
- produce about $\frac{4}{5}$ of the Global Domestic Product
- with a relatively high efficiency (consuming about 1 to 3 kWh of primary energy to produce 1 US \$ of GDP)
- consuming about 60 percent of the global input on (commercial) primary energy.

the less industrialized, developing countries of today,

- with about $\frac{3}{4}$ of the world population
- produce about $\frac{1}{5}$ of the global GDP
- this with a comparatively low energy efficiency (consuming about 3 to 10 kWh of primary energy to produce 1 US\$ of GDP) consuming about 40% of the global input on commercial primary energy.

In the past a significant rise of the energy efficiency in many sectors, especially in:

- power plants
 - internal combustion engines of vehicles
 - construction of buildings with high efficiency for room heating and air conditioning
- mainly in the highly industrialized countries of today has helped to reduce the rising consumption of energy. This partial saving of energy –having led to a corresponding saving of financial resources- has at least partially led to a further increase of the GDP without a corresponding increase of the demand on energy.

Thus hopefully, in the future, a further possible increase of the energy efficiency in all sectors, this in the highly industrialized countries as well as especially in the developing countries of today with fast rising populations and further economic development (table 1), can help us to reduce the further rise of the demand on energy appreciably.

In most countries, the main source of commercial primary energy-on global average about 85 percent-are fossil fuels: coal, crude oil and natural gas. They are used at present

- in power plants to produce electricity (about 40%)
- for fuels in the transportation sector (about 24%)
- for manufacturing, industry, construction (about 22%)
- for room heating (about 14%).

The results are summarized in Table 1 overleaf.

YEAR 2000

Other Renewable Energy	Hydro	Nuclear	Fossil	Total Primary Energy
0.25	0.25	0.7	8	9.2 Bill.tOE

Industrial countries of today	1.5	1US\$/ 1 to 3 kWh	4/5	60 %
Develop. Countries of today	4.5	1US\$/ 3 to 10 kWh	1/5	40%
World	6	1US\$/ 2.6 kWh	42,000 Bill. US\$	100%

YEAR 2050

	Population (Bill.)	GDP/PE	GDP	PE
World	9	1US\$/ 2.2 kWh	75,000 to 100,000 Billion US\$	100%
Industrial countries of today	1.5 -2	1US\$/ 1 – 2 kWh	1/2	40%
Develop. Countries of today	7 – 7.5	1US\$/ 1 – 5 kWh	1/2	60%

Present Level	1	0.5	1 to 2	11 to 15	14 to 18 (Bill. tOE)
Cost of Renewable Energy	Other Renewable Energy	Hydro	Nuclear	Fossil	Total PE
Level Strongly Reduced	Few to many	0.5	1 to 2	12 to 16 Minus other Renewable Energies	14 to 18

Table 1 – Energy situation

(Numbers on PE, GDP, GDP/PE have been taken respectively deduced from [IAE, WEC] and from the country reports, see Annex B)

UNTIL 2050

Taking into account the differences to be expected of further growth of population and of speed of further economic development in already highly industrialized countries and in less industrialized developing countries, the share of the global GDP - at least about twice as much as today or more - between both types of countries may become about equal. The global demand of (commercial) primary energy may increase at least by about 50 to 100 percent.

Countries with a fast economic growth, wishing to improve the standard of living of their population, will find that economic growth is limited by the restricted availability of sufficient energy at a sufficiently low cost.

Concerning the further availability of fossil fuels the conventional and still relatively cheap reserves are more or less limited (see table 2). At present rates of use, coal will last about 300 years, natural gas about 70 years and oil about 40 years. Furthermore these oil and gas reserves are rather unequally dispersed around the globe: about 2/3 of the reserves of crude oil are concentrated in the Middle East countries, the reserves of natural gas are concentrated in the Middle East countries (about 30 percent) and in the countries of the former Soviet Union (about 40 percent). Only the reserves of coal are distributed more or less equally around the globe.

At the present status of energy technologies the future provision of energy from non-fossil energy sources is more or less rather limited,

- either because of limited availability (e.g. hydro power)
- and/or because of relatively high investment cost (e.g. nuclear fission power)
- or because of high respectively very high investment cost and missing availability of energy storage (e.g. wind power and photovoltaics).

Therefore fossil fuels are expected to continue to be the dominant source of primary energy at least within the next decades despite the danger of climate change.

To reconcile both confronting necessities

- to provide sufficient energy
- and to reduce further emissions of carbon dioxide from burning of fossil fuels

requires strong efforts on both:

- R & D on non fossil energy technologies
 - . nuclear fission
 - . renewable energy
 - . nuclear fusion

to gradually substitute the further use of fossil fuels within some to many decades

- R & D on clean fossil energy technologies
 - . increasing the efficiency of power plants
 - . including CO₂ sequestration and deposition

to allow fossil fuels to still be the major source of primary energy within the next decades.

This will require paying special attention:

- to the different intentions of different countries to further develop favoured special energy technologies
- to corresponding scientific and technical possibilities
- and to international cooperation in R & D

	ANNUAL CONSUMPTION AT PRESENT (2000)	RESERVES (CONVENTIONAL) PROVEN AVAILABILITY FOR ECONOMIC EXPLOITATION	RESOURCES (CONVENTIONAL & UNCONVENTIONAL) ESTIMATED AVAILABILITY WITHOUT REGARDING COST FOR EXPLOITATION
COAL	3.4 BILL. tCE	1,000 BILL. tCE	6,000 BILL. tCE
OIL	3.6 BILL. tOE	130 BILL. tOE	650 BILL. tOE
NATURAL GAS	2.5 TRILL. Nm ³	165 TRILL. Nm ³	500 TRILL. Nm ³
METHANE HYDRATES	-	-	1,500 TRILL. Nm ³ R & D*
TOTAL	8.0 BILL. tOE	967 BILL. tOE	21,000 BILL. tOE

Table 2: Fossil Fuels

* Presently some countries (e.g. U. S. A., India, Japan) investigate

[G. Bohrmann, R. Matsumoto, K. Sain]

- . the resources of methane hydrates especially in the sediments of continental sea shelves
- . a possible exploitation of these resources
- . the danger of release of methane from these resources into the atmosphere.

III-3 Summaries of R & D on energy technology reports from experts

3.1 Fossil fuels

The main efforts of R & D will be shortly described in the next few pages: they are concerned with:

- fossil fuel fired power plants (3.1.1)
(affecting 40 percent of fossil fuel consumption at present) to increase efficiency of producing electric power and to sequester and deposit carbon dioxide
[expert: Olaf Bolland, Norway]

- fossil fuel fired high temperature fuel cells (3.1.2)
[experts: H. Yokakawa, K. Tanimoto, Japan]

- liquid fossil fuels in transportation sector (3.1.3)
(affecting 24 percent of fossil fuel consumption at present) here conversion of natural gas to methanol)

- non conventional resources (3.1.4)
methane hydrates in sediments of continental sea shelves:
Concerning the risk of release of large amounts of methane into the atmosphere amplifying global warming
[expert: G. Bohrmann, Germany]
Concerning a possible exploitation of these resources
[experts: K. Sain, India, and R. Matsumoto, Japan]

3.1.1. Fossil fuel fired power plants including CO₂ sequestration and storage

(O. Bolland, Norway – see Annex AI-1)

Further development of the technologies of fossil fuel fired steam and gas turbine power plants especially to work at higher steam and gas inlet temperatures(mainly by designing and producing new materials) is expected to increase efficiency of converting high temperature heat to electric power significantly (by about 5 to 10 percent points).

But implementation of CO₂ sequestration partially via innovative methods, like membrane technologies, leads to a reduction of the overall conversion efficiency of the power plant

- via post combustion CO₂ sequestration by about 9 percent
- via pre combustion CO₂ sequestration by about 7 percent
- via oxy fuel combustion CO₂ sequestration by about 14 percent.

Table 3 summarizes expected development of the efficiency of fossil fuel fired power plants
[O. Bolland, COOR]:

3.1.3. Liquid fuels in the transportation sector: conversion of natural gas to methanol and liquefaction of coal to gasoline)

(S. Richter and U. Wagner, Germany – Annex AIV-2)

At present about 24 percent of fossil fuels are consumed for propulsion in the transportation sector. The technologies to convert natural gas to methanol and to liquefy coal to methanol and/or gasoline are available. In future -when cars with fuel cell electric motors may become available (see section 3.5) one might consider providing hydrogen (see section 3.4) for driving fuel cells from the fossil fuels with sequestration of CO₂ and its deposition

3.1.4. Non conventional resources of fossil fuels: methane hydrates in sediments of continental sea shelves

(G. Bohrmann, Germany – Annex AI-3; R. Matsumoto, Japan – Annex AI-5; , K. Sain, India-AnnexAI-4)

The amount of methane hydrates, especially in the sediments on the sea floor of continental sea shelves, has been estimated to about 1,500 trillion Nm³, corresponding to 12,000 billion tOE, about twice as much as the total conventional and non conventional resources of coal, oil and natural gas.

Concerning the possible release of methane from these sediments in the atmosphere

(G. Bohrmann- Annex AI-3):

The stability of these gas hydrate sediment deposits is only given within a narrow band of temperature and water pressure at the sea floor. Small changes of temperature and pressure can lead to a destabilization of these sediments and to corresponding release of methane finally into the atmosphere. As methane is a very climate sensitive gas such a release could increase greenhouse warming on earth significantly.

Concerning the exploration of methane hydrates and R & D towards commercial exploitation

(K. Sain, India, R. Matsumoto, Japan):

Exploration of marine gas hydrates are pursued via seismic survey, offshore exploration drilling and geochemical investigations. Different methods towards a possible economically viable mining like e.g. local depressurization and inhibitor injection are pursued together with proper hazard assessment.

3.2 Nuclear fission energy

At present about 16 percent of the global demand for electric power are met via nuclear fission power plants in 30 countries, with nuclear power plants providing from a few to about 80 percent of the local demand for electric power.

All relevant technologies for allowing a fairly economical use of nuclear fission energy, in an environmentally safe way are available, at least in principle. This holds for the whole chain of processes, from mining uranium deposits, operating nuclear power plants inherently safe with respect to the nuclear fission chain reaction as well as to the removal of the after-heat from radioactive decays after the stop of the nuclear chain reaction without any risk of a large accident (High Temperature Reactor, HTR), to finally the safe deposition of radioactive waste.

At present R & D on evolutionary improvements of nuclear power plants (NPP) to be built within the next decades (generation III NPP) are underway

- to further decrease the risk of large accidents of Light Water Reactors (LWR). The main activities are in USA, France and Japan.
- to avoid the risk of a large accident totally with HTR, inherently safe in any respect by physical principles (main activities in China, South Africa, USA, and Russia, Japan)

Furthermore R & D on revolutionary improvements of NPP to become available after many decades of further development (generation IV NPP) are studied at present, to finally develop most suitable technologies to allow provision of nuclear fission energy by very large amounts and this over a time period of at least many hundred years heading for nearly closed fuel cycle via breeding and reprocessing of fuels and heading for reducing the amount of high level radioactive waste largely either by burning all actinides in proper NPP or by transmutation of minor actinides to shorten the lifetime of radioactive waste:

- Very High Temperature Reactors (VHTR) with special emphasis on provision of hydrogen by thermo chemical catalytic water splitting
- Supercritical Water cooled Reactors (SWR)
- Lead and Sodium cooled Fast neutron Reactors with breeding potential, (LFR and SFR) heading finally for nearly closed fuel cycle
- Gas cooled Fast Reactors (GFR) and Molten Salt Reactors, (MSR), including burning of actinides from radioactive waste possible with Accelerator Driven Systems (ADS)
- Transmutation of minor actinides from high level radioactive waste either by bombardment with neutrons from a nuclear reactor or from a particle accelerator or e.g. by photo transmutation via laser driven high brightness gamma ray beams [LED].
- Thorium fuelled advanced Heavy Water Reactor, (ThHWR), and possibly other reactor types as well are studied in India (*K. Anantheraman and R.K. Sinha – AnnexA II-4*).

(These investigations are mainly pursued in an international cooperation within the Generation IV International Forum of -at present - 10 countries: USA, France, Japan, South Africa, UK, Canada, South Korea, Argentina, Brazil and Switzerland, and furthermore EURATOM. Further countries like e.g. China and India exhibit high interest in these developments.)

(*A. C. Kadak, USA – Annex AII-1. N. E. Todreas, USA – Annex A-II-3. M. Igashira, Japan – Annex AII-2*)

Furthermore, to enlarge the availability of uranium fuel (from at present some 100 years to possibly many 1000 years) an economic way to extract uranium from sea water is investigated in Japan. (*N. Seko and M. Tamada, Japan – Annex AII-5*).

The main challenge in all the further development of nuclear fission power technologies is to achieve solutions both technically and economically highly attractive, and this in environmentally safe ways.

3.3 Renewable energy

Before industrialization, renewable energy had been the only source of energy available:

- firewood to provide heat
- biomass for food, for horses and other animals for hauling transportation vehicles
- wind for propulsion of sailing boats
- wind and water power to run mills.

The onset of industrialization caused an extraordinarily fast rise of the demand on energy, caused a severe shortage of firewood in many countries. Fossil fuels soon became the dominant source of primary energy. The abundant and steady availability of fossil fuels and especially their low cost satisfied the newly arising additional demand on energy to provide any required fast rising amount of

- heat
- electric power
- fuels for propulsion in the transportation sector.

At present renewable energy can be used to provide only a rather limited amount of secondary energy, as indicated in Table 4.

	Via	Percentage of global demand	
Electric energy	Hydro power	18	} 20 %
	Wind power	0.3	
	Biomass	1	
	Geothermal	0.3	
	Sunlight	0.02	
Fuels Transportation sector	Ethanol	About 1	} 2 %
	Biodiesel	About 1	
Heat mainly for cooking in developing countries	Burning-non commercial- biomass (mainly firewood)	About 7% of the total global demand on primary energy	

Table 4: Amount of secondary energy provided by renewable energy

A more extended use of renewable energy at present is mainly handicapped

- by restricted availability (e.g. hydro power, biomass)
- by strongly fluctuating and intermittent availability of hydro river and wind power and of sunlight (see fig. 1) [STRO, WAG, GOE])
- by comparatively high investment cost and cost of energy provided (e.g. sunlight, geothermal energy).

Hydro River Power (typ. facility in Germany)

Wind Power (typ. facility at the German shore to the North Sea)

Sunlight Conversion via Photovoltaics (Freiburg, Germany)

Figure 1 - Availability of Electric Power from River Hydro [STRO], Wind [WAG] and Photovoltaic [GOE] Powerplants: Restrictions and Fluctuations in Time.

This is a challenge for R & D, making best use

- of interdisciplinary science and technology
- of nano sciences and nano technologies for design and production of new materials to achieve economically attractive solutions, as indicated in the following survey of reports from scientific experts.

3.3.1. "Solar" electric energy via photovoltaics (PV)

(A. Luque, Spain – Annex III-1)

Further R & D on PV is pursued

- on well established roads of mainly Si and furthermore Cu₂S, Cu(InGa) Se₂, CdTe technologies
- on completely new paths, including organic solar cells, to achieve much higher efficiencies and this at much lower cost
- on installing PV power systems in space in geostationary orbit - by innovative, sufficiently low cost space shuttle technologies -, thus to allow continuous provision of electric power, being transmitted to earth via microwaves directed onto ground based receiver antennas.

(H. Matsumoto and N. Shinohara, Japan – Annex AIII-3)

3.3.2. Storage of electric energy

(J. Ahearne, USA – Annex AIII-2)

Intimately connected to solar electric energy via PV on earth is the required storage of electric energy

- either directly in rechargeable batteries hoping to finally achieve much higher storage densities and this at much lower cost than at present
- or indirectly e.g. via producing and storing hydrogen (chapter 3.4) to be later used in fuel cells (chapter 3.5) to produce electric energy

Energy storage technologies - at present commercially available - are mainly Pumped Hydro Storage (globally 56 units with a total power of about 140 GW, corresponding to about 4 percent of the total installed power) and furthermore underground Compressed Air Energy Storage (2 units with a total power of 0.4 GW). These large scale energy storage technologies are most suitable for daily partially balancing the supply of electric power during the hours of high and of low demand.

3.3.3. Solar thermal power plants, STPP

(M. Romero, Spain – Annex A-III-4)

In solar thermal power plants - to be positioned in low latitude arid desert regions with high insolation - sunlight is concentrated via large area mirrors and converted to high temperature heat (of hot air or hot vapor) to then drive gas or steam turbines to produce electric power. With forthcoming possibilities of cheap storage of high temperature heat e.g. in sand STPP could provide electric power continuously, in plant units of up to about some 100 MWe

A further option of STPP, the Solar Chimney PP, is based on the idea of heating the air inside a largely extended greenhouse and letting escape the hot air through a high chimney in the

center of the greenhouse. Inside the chimney the upward draft drives a wind rotor generator. At present, a 200 MWe demonstration plant with a circular greenhouse of 7 km diameter and a chimney of 1 km height, is planned to be built near Mildura, Australia [BER].

3.3.4. *Wind power plants*

(H.-J. Wagner, R. Tryfonidou, Germany – Annex A-III-6)

The technology of wind rotor generator plants with up to a few MW max. electric power is well advanced. Major further R & D is concentrated on the development of wind rotor generator units with some MW max. electric power to be installed “offshore” in shallow ocean regions to extend the intervals of providing electric power from typically up to about 20 percent of availability in time - typical for on shore and inland wind rotor installations - to about 30 to 40 percent.

3.3.5. *Hydro Power*

Concerning Hydro Power

- the technologies of high pressure reservoir and low pressure river power plants are well established [PUER, STRO, YUAN]
- the technology of tidal power plants is available in principle and has been investigated comprehensively [WAL]. But its further realization, beyond the existing 240 MW tidal power plant at the Rance estuary in France, has been barred mainly by the rather high expenses to be expected.
- the technologies of ocean wave and ocean current power conversion still require extensive R & D both for large power facilities to be installed in the open ocean as well as for small power facilities to be installed in shallow coastal areas.

3.3.6. *Biofuels*

(R. C. Cerqueira Leite, Brazil – Annex AIII-5)

For providing ethanol from sugar cane in Brazil an energy efficiency ratio, - the ratio of the caloric energy of the biofuel to the total commercial energy input for growing biomass and its conversion to biofuel - of about 8 has been obtained. For producing ethanol, methanol or biodiesel from other kinds of biomass the energy efficiency ratio obtained so far is much lower. Providing biofuel from biomass may be rather promising for countries with proper large areas of land suitable for agricultural energy crops at present like e.g. Brazil. On a global scale the bottle neck for providing a large fraction of the demand on liquid fuels for the transportation sector is the limited availability of sufficient areas for agricultural land to provide sufficient amounts of food for a world population, expected to rise from about 6 to at least about 9 billion humans.

To further enlarge the total area of agricultural land by a significant amount extensive R & D is required towards re-cultivation of sufficiently large areas of arid land including the provision of water for artificial irrigation by desalination and purification - this at sufficiently low cost -, this artificial irrigation at least for some time, till the re-cultivation to green land may change the local climate to obtain sufficient natural precipitation.

3.3.7. Geothermal energy

The use of the rather limited resources of geothermal energy from natural hot water and vapour wells as well as the withdrawal of hot water from deep aquifer layers via artificial bore holes is established. Rather limited R & D is pursued to withdraw heat from deep hot dry respectively wet rock layers - e.g. in Soultz-sous-Forêts in France - via drilling boreholes into 3 to 5 km depth, impressing water through one of the boreholes and to withdraw vapor at temperatures of 120 to 200 degrees Celsius through a second borehole [CLA].

3.4 Hydrogen

(W. E. Evenson, USA – Annex AIV-1; S. Richter and U. Wagner, Germany- Annex AIV-2; K. Onuki and M. Ogawa, Japan – Annex AIV-3; J. Samseth, Norway – AnnexAIV-4. C. Beckervordersandforth, Germany – Annex AIV-5)

Hydrogen is a secondary energy carrier to possibly be provided from any type of primary energy respectively of secondary energy like electric energy or high temperature heat. At present about 50 million t hydrogen/anno (with a caloric value corresponding to 140 million tOE or about 10 percent of the present demand on liquid fuels in the transportation sector) are produced globally from natural gas. The provision of hydrogen in the chain electrolysis, liquefaction, storage and distribution requires the expenditure of at least 2 kWh electric energy for 1 kWh caloric energy of hydrogen provided. Therefore a provision of large amounts of hydrogen via electrolysis would require a corresponding large rise of the demand on electric energy.

For future provision of hydrogen by large amounts rather challenging R & D along different new ways is required and is partially already going on, e.g.

- photo electrolysis (by special PV cells)
- solar thermal \
- photo chemical - catalytic
- photo biological - water splitting
- thermo chemical /

To provide hydrogen as an innovative fuel in the transportation sector to a large scale economic solutions for stationary and mobile storage, handling, transportation and distribution have yet to be found.

As an alternative to the difficult handling of hydrogen, R & D towards converting hydrogen directly at the location of its production via synthesis with CO₂ extracted from the atmosphere to a proper synfuel like e.g. methanol may finally lead to avoid the expensive infrastructure of a future hydrogen economy [LACK].

3.5 Low temperature fuel cells

(C. Cremers and U. Stimming, Germany – Annex AV-1)

Low temperature fuel cells, especially Polymer Electrolyte Membrane Fuel Cells, PEMFC, and Direct Methanol Fuel Cells, DMFC, are regarded as forthcoming future technologies for mobile provision of electric power especially on board of fuel cell electric motor vehicles.

Further challenging, rather imaginative R & D is required to overcome the many difficulties at present, especially

- to improve membrane materials for higher operation temperatures
- to improve the catalyst structures
- to increase conversion efficiency
- to achieve higher power density
- to improve systems designs
- to enlarge choice of useable fuels
- to take into consideration bio-electrochemical fuel cells
- and last not least to reduce the cost of fuel cells by up to two orders of magnitude to become competitive with present vehicle propulsion by internal combustion engines.

3.6 Nuclear fusion energy

(R. Fonck, USA – Annex AVI-1; P. K. Kaw, India – Annex AIV-2; C. Hidalgo, Spain – Annex AIV-3; B. Richter, USA – Annex AIV-5; K. Mima, Japan – Annex AIV-4)

Concerning the possible use of *nuclear fusion energy* by means of nuclear fusion power plants, up till now only fusion processes in principle, rather limited in power and in operation time, have been achieved so far.

Further necessary steps of the technology development of nuclear fusion power plants are

- to achieve the necessary high fusion power over sufficient long operation time
- to develop proper materials with sufficient stability for the first wall of the fusion vessel
- to extract the rather high thermal power from the walls of the fusion vessel
- to breed the necessary tritium fuel for fusion by neutron lithium interactions inside the walls of the fusion vessel and to extract it
- finally to prove the technology of a nuclear fusion power plant to be sufficiently economic.

To achieve the required goals, rather different options of fusion technologies are pursued at present:

- magnetic confinement of the hot fusion plasma, initially heated up with HF and neutral atom beams (TOKAMAK : ITER, STELLARATOR)
- inertial confinement of the fusion plasma initially heated up with lasers and laser generated x-rays, with “z-pinch” electric pulse generated x-rays, with heavy ion beams.

And there may be further options initiating fusion to become available like e.g. muon catalytic fusion including the recovery of muons sticking to helium nuclei produced by fusion of deuteron and tritium nuclei [NAG] or initiating the heating of a fusion plasma via standing acoustic waves leading to strong compression shock waves [TAL].

To achieve the goals via any of these options, at least 2 to 3 further successive steps of R & D are required, mainly at test facilities and demonstration plants. Each step is rather expensive in manpower and cost and will require a time span of 1 to 2 decades for construction and operation. The high expenditures call for international collaborations to pursue these options.

The option, most advanced at present, is Magnetic Confinement Fusion with a Tokamak device: The International Thermonuclear Experimental Reactor, ITER, is the next step along

this line and is being planned by an international collaboration of scientists and engineers from the European Union, Japan, Russia, USA, China and South Korea.

Hopefully all possible promising options of fusion technologies will be pursued until at least one of them has led to a viable technical as well as economical solution.

IV-CONCLUSIONS – OUTLOOK

It is an important and exciting task of physics concerning R & D on energy technologies, to discover and prepare new ways based on brilliant ideas, making use of computational physics, nano sciences and nano technologies to provide any secondary energy demanded from any kind of primary energy

- in sufficient amount
- in an environmentally safe way, especially
 - . on one hand to fight climate change and to limit respectively to avoid the threatening high cost of damages by climate change
 - . on the other hand to reduce respectively to avoid the risk of large accidents at nuclear power plants
- at sufficient low cost

meeting the still rising demand on energy mainly caused by economically fast developing countries where the restricted availability of energy is a limiting factor for further development.

A large variety of energy technologies can be tackled by challenging R & D covering nearly any branch of modern physics but also chemistry and material science, never restricted to one branch alone, always basic physics and applied physics linked together inseparably.

R & D of some of these technologies may require investments of only some 100 human years (like possibly innovative photovoltaics and battery storage). Others may require investments of some 100,000 human years (like fusion power and photovoltaics power in space). Nevertheless all of these technologies have to be investigated further.

There is high interest in any of the innovative energy technologies in many countries around the globe including OECD countries as well as especially countries with high and fast rising populations like e.g. China, India, Brazil. (These 3 countries together –representing at present 40 percent of the world population- cause already nearly 20 percent of the global demand on energy and this share may well increase to about 50 percent within the forthcoming decades.)

Different countries put different emphasis on improving the use of the different sources of primary energy, fossil fuels, nuclear fission, renewable energy and nuclear fusion. But all countries look for appropriate scientific cooperation in R & D of energy technologies of their choice.

To be kept in mind: fossil fuels will continue to be the dominant source of primary energy at least within the next few decades. It will take some to many decades to improve the use of other sources of primary energy like e.g. nuclear fission and renewable energy to be able to play a much more important role to satisfy our demand on energy than nowadays. This is intimately linked to the ability to cut cost of providing energy from nuclear and especially from renewable energy appreciably, and concerning the increased use of renewable energy with strongly intermittent availability to find new ways to store energy -especially electric energy -efficiently and cost effectively. Nuclear fusion energy may become an option only in the far more distant future of many decades.

Therefore R & D on clean fossil fuel technologies with highest possible efficiencies and including CO₂ sequestration and storage respectively use is of utmost importance.

V- ANNEX A: LIST OF EXPERT REPORTS ON R & D OF SPECIAL ENERGY TECHNOLOGIES

I. Fossil Energy

AI-1. Power Generation with CO₂ Capture and Sequestration

Olaf Bolland, Norwegian University of Science and Technology, Trondheim, Norway

AI-2. Future needs for fundamental research in the oil and gas industry especially on non conventional resources

Jon Samseth, SINTEF, Norway

AI-3. Oceanic Hydrates, a dynamic reservoir of methane within the marine environment

Gerhard Bohrmann, Department of Geosciences, University of Bremen, Germany

AI-4. Methane Hydrates: Present Status of worldwide R & D on the utilisation of Gas Hydrates for Power Production

Kalachand Sain, National Geophysical Research Institute, Hyderabad, India

AI-5. Exploration of Marine Gas Hydrates around Japanese Islands

Ryo Matsumoto, Earth and Planetary Science, University of Tokyo, Japan

II. Nuclear Fission Energy

AII-1. New Nuclear Energy Plant Designs

Andrew C. Kadak, Professor of the Practice, MIT, Cambridge, US

AII-2. R & D Needs of Fission Energy Generation

Neil E. Todreas, MIT, Cambridge, US

AII-3. Physics Based R & D for Innovative Fission Reactors

Masayuki Igashira, Research Laboratory for Nuclear Reactors, Tokyo Institute of Technology, Japan

AII-4. Present Status of worldwide R & D on the Utilisation of Thorium for Power Production

K. Anantharaman and R. K. Sinha, Bhabha Atomic Research Center, Trombay, Mumbai, India

AII-5. R & D towards Recovery of Uranium from Sea Water

Noriaki Seko and Maseao Tamada, Takasaki RCRE, JAERI, Japan

III. Renewable Energy

AIII-1. R & D Needs in Photovoltaics

Antonio Luque, Universidad Politécnica, Madrid, Spain

AIII-2. Storage of (Electric) Energy:

-Batteries: Present and Future

-Pumped Hydro and Compressed Air Energy Storage

John Ahearne, Research Triangle Park, NC, US

AIII-3. Space Solar Power Systems: Development Status and Future Perspectives

Hiroshi Matsumoto and Naoki Shinohara, Research Institute of Sustainable Humanosphere, Kyoto University, Japan

AIII-4. Thermal Power Plants

Manuel Romero, CIEMAT, Madrid, Spain

AIII-5. Energy from Biomass

Rogério C. de Cerqueira Leite, Universidade Estadual De Campinas, Brazil

AIII-6. Wind Energy - Status and R & D Activities

Hermann-Josef Wagner and Rodoula Tryfonidou, LEE, Ruhr-Universität Bochum, Germany

IV. Hydrogen

AIV-1. The Potential for the Hydrogen Energy Economy

William E. Evenson, Brigham Young University, USA

AIV-2. R & D towards Provision of Hydrogen

Stefan Richter and Ulrich Wagner, Forschungsstelle für Energiewirtschaft und Technische Universität München, Germany

AIV-3. Report on the Thermochemical Water Splitting (via the Iodine Sulphur Cycle) at the HTTR

Kaoru Onuki and Masuro Ogawa, JAERI, Japan

AIV-4. Hydrogen Production and Storage

Jon Samseth, SINTEF, Norway

AIV-5. Use of Natural Gas Pipelines to Transport Hydrogen Gas

Christian P. Beckervordersandforth, Ruhrgas AG, Essen, Germany

V. Fuel Cells

AV-1. Low Temperature Fuel Cells: Development Status and Future Perspectives

Carsten Cremers and Ulrich Stimming, Bavarian Center of Applied Energy Research, TU Munich, Germany

AV-2. Solid Oxide Fuel Cells

Harumi Yokakawa, National Institute of Advanced Industrial Science and Technology, AIST, Japan

AV-3. Technolgical Status of Molten Carbonate Fuel Cell

K. Tanimoto, National Institute of Advanced Industrial Science and Technology, Japan

VI. Nuclear Fusion Energy

AVI-1. R & D Opportunities for Fusion Energy

Ray Fonck, University of Wisconsin, Madison, USA

AVI-2. Fusion Energy using TOKAMAKs

Predhiman K. Kaw, Institute for Plasma Research, Bhat, Gandhinagar, India

AVI-3. Physics Issues on Magnetically Confined Plasmas: Stellarator Devices

Carlos Hidalgo, EURATOM-CIEMAT, Madrid, Spain

AVI-4. Status Report on Inertial Energy Fusion

Burton Richter, Stanford University, USA

AVI-5. Report on Laser Fast Ignition for Inertial Fusion Energy

Kunioki Mima, Institute of Laser Engineering, Osaka University, Japan

VI-ANNEX B: LIST OF COUNTRY REPORTS ON THEIR SPECIAL ENERGY SITUATION

-P. R. China	Huo Yuping
-India	P. K. Kaw
-Brazil	R. C. Cerqueira Leite
-USA	J. F. Ahearne
-Germany	K. Heinloth
-Russia	O. N. Favorskyi
-Japan	Y. Nagai
-France	H. Nifenecker
-Southern European Countries (Italy, Spain and Portugal)	F. Yndurain
-Nordic European Countries (Iceland, Norway, Denmark, Sweden, Finland)	J. Samseth
-South Africa	T. Alfstad,

VII-REFERENCES (besides the reports from experts attached)

- BER** M. A. dos S. Bernardes et. al, Thermal and technical analyses of solar chimneys, *Solar Energy* 75 (2003) 511 - 524
- BGR** German Federal Agency for Geoscience and Natural Resources: Reserves, Resources and Availability of Energy Raw Materials, Hannover 1998
- BRO** Brockhaus Encyclopaedia, Mannheim 1987
- CLA** C. Clauser, Geothermal Energy, In HEI, Subvolume C
- COOR** COORETEC: Research and Development Concept for Zero-Emission Fossil Fuelled Power Plants, Documentation Nr. 527, German Federal Ministry of Economics and Labour, Berlin 2003
- GOE** A. Goetzberger, Photovoltaic Power Generation, in HEI, Subvolume C
- HEI** K. Heinloth (Editor), Energy Technologies, Landolt-Börnstein, Group VIII, Volume 3, Subvolume A (Fossil Energy), 2003, Subvolume B (Nuclear Energy), 2004, Subvolume C (Renewable Energy, to be published 2005), Springer Publ. Co, Berlin 2003/2004/2005
- IEA** World Energy Outlook 2002, CO₂ emissions from fuel combustion, 2003
- IPCC** Intergovernmental Panel on Climate Change, 1st, 2nd and 3rd Assessment Report, Cambridge 1991, 1996, 2001
- LACK** K. S. Lackner, Zero Emission Coal Alliance, ZECA, Columbia Univ., NY, USA, 2003
- LED** K. W. D. Ledingham et al., Laserdriven photo-transmutation ..., *J. Phys. D: Appl. Phys.* 36 (2003) L 79 - 82
- NAG** K. Nagamine, Muon Catalyzed Fusion in HEI, Subvolume B
- PUER** E. Puerer and G. Gökler, Hydroelectric Reservoir Power Plants, in HEI, Subvolume C
- STRO** T. Strobl and F. Zunic, Hydroelectric River Powerplants, in HEI, Subvolume C
- TAL** R. P. Taleyarkhan et al., *Science* Vol. 295, p. 1868, March 2002 and 2004 *Phys. Rev. E* 69, 036109
- WAG** H.-J. Wagner, Windelectric Power, in HEI, Subvolume C
- WAL** W. van Walsum and Won-Oh Song, Tidal Power Plants, in HEI, Subvolume C
- WEC** World Energy Council, 2004
- YUAN** Yuan Dafu, Tian Ziqin, Wang Shuqing, Mechanical and Electrical Design of the Three Gorges Project, in HEI, Subvolume C

Annex A: Expert reports on R & D of special Energy Technologies
<http://www.iupap.org/>

Annex B: Country reports on their special energy situation
<http://www.iupap.org/>

VIII-USEFUL ABBREVIATIONS AND DEFINITIONS

1-Energy Units

- Joule:J
- Btu=British thermal unit= $1,055.10^3$ J=1,055 kJ
- kWh= $3,600.10^6$ J=3,6 MJ, kWh_e=kWh electric, kWh_{th}=kWh thermal
- tOE=ton of oil equivalent= 42.10^9 J=42 GJ
- tCE=ton of coal equivalent= $29,3.10^9$ J=29,3 GJ
- MWh= $3,6.10^9$ J=3,6 GJ

2-Power Units

- Watt:W
- Btu/hour=Btu/h=0,29 W

3-Volume

- Nm³=10³ liter under normal conditions of pressure and temperature
- petroleum barrel= $1,59.10^{-1}$ m³
- bOE= barrel of oil equivalent

4-Symbols

- P=Peta= 10^{15}
- T=Tera= 10^{12}
- G=Giga= 10^9
- M=Mega= 10^6
- k=kilo= 10^3

5-Definitions

- Fuel Cell: a cell in which electricity is produced through the oxidation of a fuel (methanol,...).
- Natural and Enriched Uranium (U). Natural Uranium is made of 99,27 % of ²³⁸U, 0,72 % of ²³⁵U and 0,005 % of ²³⁴U: to be able to function , a reactor must have 3,5 to 4,4 % of ²³⁵U. This operation is called enrichment.
- NPP: Nuclear Power Plant: it is composed of:
 - . the fuel core : natural U, enriched UO₂, UO₂-PuO₂....).
 - . the moderator : it is a material that slows the velocity of neutrons so they may be absorbed by nuclei: ordinary water, heavy water, graphite....).
 - . the coolant: it can be a gas (CO₂ or He) or a liquid (light water-pressurized or boiling, heavy water-pressurized, sodium....).There are various types but most of the plants are light water reactors, using the steam cycle to generate electricity with pressurized or boiling water.
some examples: LWR (Light Water Reactor), BWR (Boiling Water Reactor), AWBR (Advanced Boiling Water Reactor), HTR (High Temperature Reactor),

VHTR (Very High Temperature Reactor), MSR (Molten Salt Reactor), SCWR (Supercritical Water Cooled Reactor), BREEDER (reactor designed to produce more fissionable fuel at faster rate than it consumes fuel for electricity production).

- Tokamak: toroidal device in which a gas of deuterium and tritium is heated to produce nuclear reactions of fusion of the nuclei. ITER is the next generation.
- Stellarator: high temperature plasma device with a racetrack shape
- Tritium: isotope of hydrogen with an atomic mass of 3.

International Union of Pure and Applied Physics

To stimulate and facilitate international cooperation in physics and the worldwide development of science.

General Assembly
Major Resolutions
Members/Liaisons
Executive Council ▶
Commissions ▶
Working Groups
Sponsored ▶
Conferences ▶
Statutes & ▶
Bylaws ▶
News Bulletins
Related Websites
Contact IUPAP

IUPAP Mission

To assist in the worldwide development of physics, to foster international cooperation in physics, and to help in the application of physics toward solving problems of concern to humanity. [More about IUPAP.](#)

Events and Conferences

IUPAP 25th General Assembly

October 26-28, 2005
Cape Town, South Africa

World Conference on Physics and Sustainable Development

October 31-November 2, 2005
Durban, South Africa

The World Year of Physics 2005 is a United Nations endorsed, international celebration of physics. [International Website](#) | [U.S. Website](#)

Upcoming Commission Conferences

- [C12.1 International Conference on Particles and Nuclei 2005](#)
October 22-28, 2005, Santa Fe, NM USA
- [C19.1 Scientific Requirements for Extremely Large Telescopes](#)
November 14-18, 2005, Cape Town, South Africa
- [All 2005 Conferences](#)

IUPAP News

New Study: **Energy Report**

- [Report](#)
- [Annex A](#)
- [Annex B](#)

Council and Commissions: Recent Reports

- [Reports of the IUPAP Commissions Prepared for the 25th General Assembly CapeTown, South Africa October 2005](#)

New Working Groups

- [International Cooperation In Nuclear Physics \(ICNP\)](#)
- [Nanoscience Working Group](#)
- [International Committee for Ultra-High Intensity Laser - ICUIL](#)

[News Archives](#)

[Contact IUPAP](#) | [Search IUPAP](#) | [IUPAP Home](#)

REPORT ON RESEARCH AND DEVELOPMENT OF ENERGY TECHNOLOGIES

**EDITED BY
IUPAP WORKING GROUP ON ENERGY**

OCTOBER 6, 2004

SUMMARY

SUMMARY	2
I - PREFACE	3
II – EXECUTIVE SUMMARY	5
<i>II-1 Renewable Energy</i>	6
<i>II-2 Hydrogen and Fuel Cells</i>	7
<i>II-3 Fossil Energy</i>	7
<i>II-4 Nuclear Fission Energy</i>	8
<i>II-5 Nuclear Fusion Energy</i>	8
<i>II-6 Conclusions - Outlook</i>	8
III-REPORT	9
<i>III-1.Introduction</i>	9
<i>III-2 Conclusions on the energy situation from reports in different selected countries and from global projections</i>	12
<i>III-3 Summaries of R & D on energy technology reports from experts</i>	16
3.1 Fossil fuels	16
3.1.1.Fossil fuel fired power plants including CO ₂ sequestration and storage.....	16
3.1.2.Fossil fuels fired high temperature fuel cells	17
3.1.3.Liquid fuels in the transportation sector: conversion of natural gas to methanol	18
3.1.4.Non conventional resources of fossil fuels: methane hydrates in sediments of continental sea shelves.....	18
3.2 Nuclear fission energy	18
3.3 Renewable energy	19
3.3.1. “Solar” electric energy via photovoltaics (PV).....	22
3.3.2.Storage of electric energy	22
3.3.3.Solar thermal power plants, STPP	22
3.3.4.Wind power plants	23
3.3.5.Hydro Power.....	23
3.3.6.Biofuels	23
3.3.7.Geothermal energy.....	24
3.4 Hydrogen	24
3.5 Low temperature fuel cells.....	24
3.6 Nuclear fusion energy	25
IV-CONCLUSIONS – OUTLOOK	27
V- ANNEX A: LIST OF EXPERT REPORTS ON R & D OF SPECIAL ENERGY TECHNOLOGIES	28
VI-ANNEX B: LIST OF COUNTRY REPORTS ON THEIR SPECIAL ENERGY SITUATION	34
VIII-USEFUL ABBREVIATIONS AND DEFINITIONS	36

I – PREFACE

The general assembly of IUPAP, in Berlin in October 2002, formed a Working Group on Energy, to which it gave the task to provide:

a survey of Research and Development (R & D) of Energy Technologies toward the future provision of any kind of secondary energy* demanded:

- electric energy
- fuels in transportation sector
- high and low temperature heat

Obviously they must be all in sufficient amounts, environmentally safe and at sufficiently low cost by making best use of any kind of primary energy including

- fossil fuels (oil, gas, coal)
- nuclear fission energy (produced in a nuclear reactor by dividing the nucleus of an atom
- nuclear fusion energy (produced by the fusion of two atomic nuclei)
- renewable energy

This survey of R & D of Energy Technologies should help to sharpen the interest

- of scientists, especially physicists, in universities, in research institutions, in industry to devote their further work to this challenging field of science
- of media people to inform the public with sufficient completeness on this subject of vital importance
- of policy makers on the attractive potential for future ample business opportunities in the field of energy technologies as well as in many other fields.

To produce this report

- we invited scientific experts of different countries to provide short surveys of many different energy technologies describing the present status as well as the future R & D required to further develop the corresponding technology for proper ample use in the future
- we have further collected reports on the special energy situation in different countries around the globe concerning
 - . the present demand on energy
 - . the possible future demand on energy together with ideas how this demand can be met
 - . the availability of different kinds of primary energy to provide any kind of secondary energy demanded
 - . the needs of further R & D on future energy technologies

We ourselves have briefly summarized the manifold energy technologies and the collected reports on the energy situation in different countries. Furthermore we have drawn conclusions on the further need of R & D of energy technologies towards future provision of energy in sufficient amount, environmentally safe and at sufficient low cost, keeping in mind that availability of energy is a limiting factor to further economic development especially in many fast developing countries around the globe.

* Examples of secondary energy: electricity, heat, gasoline.

We would like to thank the scientific experts for their most informative contribution on special energy technologies and Herve Nifenecker and T. Alfstad for their country reports on the energy situation in France respectively and in South Africa.

To read more easily this report, some units and definitions are given on page 36..

Prof. Klaus Heinloth, Chair, Bonn University
heinloth@physik.uni-bonn.de

Prof. Burton Richter, IUPAP Representative,
Stanford University brichter@slac.stanford.edu

Prof. Y. Nagai, Osaka University
nagai@rcnp.osaka-u.ac.jp

Prof. Felix Yndurain, Universidad Autonoma de Madrid
felix.yndurain@uam.es

Prof. Jon Samseth, Norwegian Physical Society
jon.samseth@sintef.no

Prof. Rogerio Cerqueira Leite, Campinas University
cerqueiraleite@uol.com.br

Prof. John Ahearne, Duke University
ahearne@sigmaxi.org

Prof. Yuping Huo, Chinese Academy of Sciences
huoyp@zzu.edu.cn

Prof. P. K. Kaw, Institute for Plasma Research-India
kaw@ipr.res.in

Prof. O. N. Favorskyi, Russian Academy of Sciences
ptped@ipsun.ras.ru

II – EXECUTIVE SUMMARY

The world population of about six billion humans (at present) is expected to culminate to about nine billion humans around the middle of this century, this further increase mainly due to developing countries with fast rising populations and fast economic development as well like e.g. China, India and Brazil. In the same period the global Gross Domestic Product (GDP) is expected to further rise by at least about a factor 2 to 3, an appreciable fraction of it by fast developing countries like mentioned. With hopefully further rising energy efficiency - like in the past - to be achieved in already industrialized countries as well as especially in developing countries the further increase of the global demand on energy may be limited to about a factor 1.5 to 2.

To achieve this required provision of energy calls for [physics achievements in the future](#) by proper R & D of energy technologies

- to further provide sufficient secondary energy (electric energy, fuels in transportation sector, high and low temperature heat) with hopefully further appreciable increase of the energy efficiency allowing the development necessary to improve the life of people around the globe, especially in countries with further strong population growth, e.g. China and India
- by proper use of available primary energy sources (fossil fuels ,nuclear fission, renewable energy, nuclear fusion)
 - . in an environmentally safe way reducing, respectively avoiding risks of nuclear energy as well as reducing, limiting risks and dangers of climate change
 - . adaptable to possible changing environmental conditions not to be foreseen now
 - . and last but not least at sufficiently low cost.

Presently the main source of commercial primary energy (on global average about 85 %) are the fossil fuels, coal, crude oil and natural gas.

At the present status of energy technologies, the future provision of energy from non-fossil energy sources is more or less rather limited,

- either because of limited availability (e.g. hydro power)
- and/or because of relatively high investment cost (e.g. nuclear fission power)
- or because of very high investment costs and missing availability of energy storage (e.g. wind power and photovoltaics)

Therefore fossil fuels are expected to continue to be the dominant source of primary energy at least within the next decades despite the danger of climate change.

To reconcile both confronting necessities (providing sufficient energy and reducing further emission of carbon dioxide from burning of fossil fuels) requires strong efforts on both

- R & D on non fossil energy technologies
 - . nuclear fission
 - . nuclear fusion
 - . renewable energy
- to gradually substitute the further use of fossil fuels within some to many decades

- R & D on clean fossil energy technologies
 - . increasing the efficiency of power plants
 - . including CO₂ sequestration and depositionto allow fossil fuels to still be the major source of primary energy within the next decades.

This is an area where a very large effort has to be made. One has to be pragmatic: some countries such as China and India have very large populations and very large reserves of coal and it is clear that they will continue to use it. So, it is absolutely necessary to increase the efficiency of power plants including CO₂ sequestration and deposition, to allow fossil fuels to still be the major source of primary energy within the next decades.

It is an important and exciting task of physics (and other disciplines) concerning R & D on energy technologies, to discover and prepare new ways based on brilliant ideas, making use of computational physics, nano sciences and nano technologies to provide any secondary energy demanded from any kind of primary energy.

A large variety of energy technologies can be tackled by challenging R & D covering nearly any branch of modern physics, never restricted to one branch alone, always basic physics and applied physics linked together inseparably. This should include strong collaborations with other disciplines like chemistry, biology, computer and material science.

II-1 Renewable Energy

Further R & D on “solar” electric energy via photovoltaics (PV) is pursued on well established paths as well as on completely new roads to achieve much higher efficiencies and this at much lower cost.

Intimately connected to solar electric energy via PV is the required storage of electric energy

- either directly in rechargeable batteries hoping to finally achieve much higher storage densities and this at much lower cost than at present
- or indirectly e.g. via producing and storing hydrogen to be later used in fuel cells to produce electric energy

A further option of solar electric energy is the solar thermal power plant - restricted to low latitude arid regions with high insolation - especially with possible cheap storage of high temperature heat to provide electric power continuously.

Major further R & D on wind power is concentrated on the development of wind rotor generator units with some MW max. electric power to be installed “offshore” in shallow ocean regions to extend the intervals of providing electric power from typically up to about 20 percent of availability in time (typical for on shore and inland wind rotor installations) to about 30 to 40 percent.

Concerning hydro power

- the technologies of high pressure reservoir and low pressure river power plants are well established
- the technology of tidal power plants is available in principle and has been investigated comprehensively. But its further realization, beyond the existing 240 MW tidal power plant at the Rance estuary in France, has been barred mainly by the rather high expenses to be expected.
- the technologies of ocean wave and ocean current power conversion still require extensive R & D both for large power facilities to be installed in the open ocean as well as for small power facilities to be installed in shallow coastal areas.

To provide [biofuel from biomass](#) may be rather promising for countries with proper large areas of land suitable for agricultural energy crops at present like e.g. Brazil. On a global scale the bottle neck for providing a large fraction of the demand on liquid fuels for the transportation sector is the limited availability of sufficient areas for agricultural land to provide sufficient amounts of food for a world population, expected to rise from about 6 to at least about 9 billion humans.

II-2 Hydrogen and Fuel Cells

[Hydrogen](#) is a secondary energy carrier to possibly be provided from any type of primary energy respectively of secondary energy like electric energy or high temperature heat. For future provision of hydrogen by large amounts, rather challenging R & D along different new ways is required and, is partially already ongoing, e.g.

- photo electrolysis (by special PV cells)
- solar thermal \
- photo chemical - catalytic
- photo biological - water splitting
- thermo chemical /

As an [alternative](#) to the difficult handling of hydrogen, R & D towards converting hydrogen directly at the location of its production via synthesis with CO₂ extracted from the atmosphere to a [proper synfuel](#) like e.g. methanol, may finally lead to avoid the expensive infrastructure of a future hydrogen economy.

Low temperature [fuel cells](#), especially Polymer Electrolyte Membrane Fuel Cells (PEMFC) and Direct Methanol Fuel Cells (DMFC) are regarded as forthcoming future technologies for mobile provision of electric power especially on board of fuel cell electric motor vehicles.

Further challenging, rather imaginative R & D is required to overcome the many difficulties at present, last not least to reduce the cost of fuel cells by up to 2 orders of magnitude to become competitive with present vehicle propulsion by internal combustion engines.

II-3 Fossil Energy

Challenging R & D is required to do the splits between:

- limiting the further increase of the CO₂ content of the atmosphere

- and making innovative use of conventional and non conventional resources of fossil fuels and especially to do the splits between
- increasing the efficiency of fossil fuel fired power plants
- and implementing innovative CO₂ sequestration and deposition.

II-4 Nuclear Fission Energy

R & D is aiming towards

- evolutionary improvements of nuclear power plants to be built in the near future by further decrease of the of the risk of a large accident of Light Water Reactors and by avoiding the risk of a large accident completely by making use of inherently safe High Temperature Reactors
- revolutionary improvements of nuclear power plants to become available after many decades, perhaps heading finally for nearly closed fuel cycles via breeding and reprocessing of fuel and for reducing the radioactive waste largely by transmutation to shorten the lifetime of radioactive waste, if these technologies can become economic.

II-5 Nuclear Fusion Energy

Further necessary R & D for at least some more decades towards finally a technically as well as economically acceptable solution of fusion power plants is pursued at present with rather different options of fusion technologies

- magnetic confinement of the fusion plasma via TOKAMAK (next step: ITER) and STELLARATOR magnet configurations
- inertial confinement of the fusion plasma via LASER generated x-rays, electric pulse generated x-rays and heavy ion beams

until hopefully at least one of these options or even a further option like e.g. muon catalytic fusion leads to an acceptable solution.

II-6 Conclusions - Outlook

To be kept in mind: fossil fuels will continue to be the dominant source of primary energy at least within the next few decades. It will take some to many decades to improve the use of other sources of primary energy like e.g. nuclear fission and renewable energy to be able to play a much more important role to satisfy our demand on energy than nowadays. This is intimately linked to the ability to cut cost of providing energy from nuclear and especially from renewable energy appreciably, and -concerning the increased use of renewable energy with strongly intermittent availability- to find new ways to store energy, especially electric energy efficiently and cost effectively.

Nuclear fusion energy may become an option only in the far more distant future of many decades. Therefore R & D on clean fossil fuel technologies with highest possible efficiencies and including CO₂ sequestration and storage respectively use is of utmost importance.

III-REPORT

III-1 Introduction

The development of early mankind for some million years was extremely slow leading to a rise of the world population to a few million humans at the end of the last glacial period about 13,000 years ago [BRO].

Since the onset of the present interglacial warm period mankind was able for the first time to settle down, to provide increasingly more food by agriculture and cattle breeding, this because of the warm climate with its unusual stability in average temperature. During the 13,000 years up till about 300 years ago, the world population rose from a few million to about 600 million humans.

With the onset of the industrialization, since 300 to 200 years ago, the world population rose extremely fast from 600 million to already more than 6,000 million humans at present.

The industrialization has been made possible by outstanding achievements of technology and science, especially physics, for example:

- steam engine by J. Watt (1769)
- electric generator and motor by W. v. Siemens (1866)
- coal fired power plants including an extended electric grid by H. Stinnes (1898)
- ICE motor car by C. + B. Benz (1888) for everybody by H. Ford (1903)
- electric battery by A. Volta (1798)
- electromagnetism by J. C. Maxwell (1861)
- electric light bulb by T. Edison (1879)
- electromagnetic waves by H. Hertz (1887)
- electron by J. J. Thomson (1892)
- transistor by J. Bardeen, W. H. Brattain, W. Shockley (1948)
- fast rising provision of food:
 - . artificial fertilizer by F. Haber (1909)
 - . high yield corn and wheat by N. E. Borlaug (1960).

Many of these and many more achievements led to a multiplication of man power by artificial power, making rapidly rising use of fossil fuels

- coal since about 1700
- crude oil since about 1900
- natural gas since about 1950

These have been the main sources of energy because of their ample and steady, non fluctuating availability and -last not least- their relatively low cost compared to availability and cost of renewable energy used so far.

Within the last 100 years the global annual demand on primary energy rose from about 1 billion tons of coal equivalent (1BtCE) to about 14 billion at present, of which

78 percent is from fossil fuels

6 percent is from nuclear energy

6 percent is from commercial renewable energy

10 percent is from non commercial renewably energy.

Now, if we have a look into the future:

the further rising world population is expected to culminate with about 9,000 million humans around mid of this century. At present nearly 2/3 of the total demand on energy is by industrialized countries with about 1/4 of the world population. Since many more countries, especially those with already high and still fast rising populations like e.g. China, India and Brazil exhibit fast rising economic development, the future global demand on energy is expected to rise by at least 50 percent within the next several decades.

The further availability (from today's knowledge) of fossil fuels is restricted at present rates of consumption

- conventional crude oil to about 4 more decades
- conventional natural gas to about 7 more decades
- conventional coal to a few hundred years.

Furthermore, it is of utmost importance to address climate change caused by climate warming induced by the exuberant burning of fossil fuels [IPCC]: the direct release of heat by burning fossil fuels - globally only less than 0.01 percent of global warming by sunlight - is negligible. Not negligible, but highly dangerous is the increase of greenhouse warming due to the increase of the content of the atmosphere on carbon dioxide: when burning fossil fuels about half of the carbon dioxide released remains in the atmosphere for at least some hundred years. Since burning fossil fuels as the main source of energy required by mankind, the carbon dioxide content of the atmosphere has been increased by about 1/3, from 0.28 per mille of volume about 200 years ago to 0.37 per mille at present. Mainly this rise has led to an additional greenhouse warming on global average by about 1 percent compared to insolation of light, which has already caused a rise of the temperature on global average by close to 1 degree Celsius.

With still further rising consumption of fossil fuels with unrestricted release of carbon dioxide during the next decades we have to expect a further rise of the temperature by some more degrees. This rise of temperature poses the risk of climate changes most dangerous to mankind and to nature in many to most regions around the globe:

For instance:

- the unusual stability of the global mean temperature, allowing agriculture and cattle breeding to provide sufficient food for at present 6 billion humans, may suddenly change to a climate with rapid fluctuations of the mean temperature, similar to that of the preceding interglacial warm period between 130,000 to 115,000 years ago.
- the north polar ice cap may melt at least partially, leading to at least a strong reduction of the intensity of the gulf current rather suddenly –which transfers enough heat mainly from the equatorial Caribbean region to western and northern Europe, to additionally heat these regions by several degrees Celsius. This would lead to a decrease of the average temperature in Europe by several degrees, significantly impacting agriculture and forestry.
- In the case of a melting of the west Antarctic ice shield –which has happened during the previous interglacial warm period at a temperature on global and long-term average of only about one to a few degrees above the present average temperature on earth– the sea

level would rise by about five meters flooding coastal areas where about one third of the world population is living at present

To fight global warming sufficiently, the further rise of the average temperature has to be limited as much as still possible, certainly to less than a few more degrees. This calls for a strong reduction of the release of carbon dioxide from further burning of fossil fuels on global average to less than ½ of the release at present, to be achieved hopefully within the next few decades.

To achieve this goal calls for [physics achievements in the future](#) by proper R & D of energy technologies

- to further provide sufficient secondary energy (electric energy, fuels in transportation sector, high and low temperature heat) with hopefully further appreciable increase of the energy efficiency allowing the development necessary to improve the life of people around the globe, especially in countries with further strong population growth, e.g. China and India
- by proper use of available primary energy sources (fossil fuels, nuclear fission, renewable energy, nuclear fusion) in an environmentally safe way reducing, respectively avoiding risks of nuclear energy as well as reducing, limiting risks and dangers of climate change. This should be adaptable to possible changing environmental conditions not foreseen now and last but not least at sufficient low cost.

III-2 Conclusions on the energy situation from reports in different selected countries and from global projections

AT PRESENT

the highly industrialized countries of today,

- with about $\frac{1}{4}$ of the world population
- produce about $\frac{4}{5}$ of the Global Domestic Product
- with a relatively high efficiency (consuming about 1 to 3 kWh of primary energy to produce 1 US \$ of GDP)
- consuming about 60 percent of the global input on (commercial) primary energy.

the less industrialized, developing countries of today,

- with about $\frac{3}{4}$ of the world population
- produce about $\frac{1}{5}$ of the global GDP
- this with a comparatively low energy efficiency (consuming about 3 to 10 kWh of primary energy to produce 1 US\$ of GDP) consuming about 40% of the global input on commercial primary energy.

In the past a significant rise of the energy efficiency in many sectors, especially in:

- power plants
 - internal combustion engines of vehicles
 - construction of buildings with high efficiency for room heating and air conditioning
- mainly in the highly industrialized countries of today has helped to reduce the rising consumption of energy. This partial saving of energy –having led to a corresponding saving of financial resources- has at least partially led to a further increase of the GDP without a corresponding increase of the demand on energy.

Thus hopefully, in the future, a further possible increase of the energy efficiency in all sectors, this in the highly industrialized countries as well as especially in the developing countries of today with fast rising populations and further economic development (table 1), can help us to reduce the further rise of the demand on energy appreciably.

In most countries, the main source of commercial primary energy-on global average about 85 percent-are fossil fuels: coal, crude oil and natural gas. They are used at present

- in power plants to produce electricity (about 40%)
- for fuels in the transportation sector (about 24%)
- for manufacturing, industry, construction (about 22%)
- for room heating (about 14%).

The results are summarized in Table 1 overleaf.

YEAR 2000

Other Renewable Energy	Hydro	Nuclear	Fossil	Total Primary Energy
0.25	0.25	0.7	8	9.2 Bill.tOE

Industrial countries of today	1.5	1US\$/ 1 to 3 kWh	4/5	60 %
Develop. Countries of today	4.5	1US\$/ 3 to 10 kWh	1/5	40%
World	6	1US\$/ 2.6 kWh	42,000 Bill. US\$	100%

YEAR 2050

	Population (Bill.)	GDP/PE	GDP	PE
World	9	1US\$/ 2.2 kWh	75,000 to 100,000 Billion US\$	100%
Industrial countries of today	1.5 -2	1US\$/ 1 – 2 kWh	1/2	40%
Develop. Countries of today	7 – 7.5	1US\$/ 1 – 5 kWh	1/2	60%

Present Level	1	0.5	1 to 2	11 to 15	14 to 18 (Bill. tOE)
Cost of Renewable Energy	Other Renewable Energy	Hydro	Nuclear	Fossil	Total PE
Level Strongly Reduced	Few to many	0.5	1 to 2	12 to 16 Minus other Renewable Energies	14 to 18

Table 1 – Energy situation

(Numbers on PE, GDP, GDP/PE have been taken respectively deduced from [IAE, WEC] and from the country reports, see Annex B)

UNTIL 2050

Taking into account the differences to be expected of further growth of population and of speed of further economic development in already highly industrialized countries and in less industrialized developing countries, the share of the global GDP - at least about twice as much as today or more - between both types of countries may become about equal. The global demand of (commercial) primary energy may increase at least by about 50 to 100 percent.

Countries with a fast economic growth, wishing to improve the standard of living of their population, will find that economic growth is limited by the restricted availability of sufficient energy at a sufficiently low cost.

Concerning the further availability of fossil fuels the conventional and still relatively cheap reserves are more or less limited (see table 2). At present rates of use, coal will last about 300 years, natural gas about 70 years and oil about 40 years. Furthermore these oil and gas reserves are rather unequally dispersed around the globe: about 2/3 of the reserves of crude oil are concentrated in the Middle East countries, the reserves of natural gas are concentrated in the Middle East countries (about 30 percent) and in the countries of the former Soviet Union (about 40 percent). Only the reserves of coal are distributed more or less equally around the globe.

At the present status of energy technologies the future provision of energy from non-fossil energy sources is more or less rather limited,

- either because of limited availability (e.g. hydro power)
- and/or because of relatively high investment cost (e.g. nuclear fission power)
- or because of high respectively very high investment cost and missing availability of energy storage (e.g. wind power and photovoltaics).

Therefore fossil fuels are expected to continue to be the dominant source of primary energy at least within the next decades despite the danger of climate change.

To reconcile both confronting necessities

- to provide sufficient energy
- and to reduce further emissions of carbon dioxide from burning of fossil fuels

requires strong efforts on both:

- R & D on non fossil energy technologies
 - . nuclear fission
 - . renewable energy
 - . nuclear fusion

to gradually substitute the further use of fossil fuels within some to many decades

- R & D on clean fossil energy technologies
 - . increasing the efficiency of power plants
 - . including CO₂ sequestration and deposition

to allow fossil fuels to still be the major source of primary energy within the next decades.

This will require paying special attention:

- to the different intentions of different countries to further develop favoured special energy technologies
- to corresponding scientific and technical possibilities
- and to international cooperation in R & D

	ANNUAL CONSUMPTION AT PRESENT (2000)	RESERVES (CONVENTIONAL) PROVEN AVAILABILITY FOR ECONOMIC EXPLOITATION	RESOURCES (CONVENTIONAL & UNCONVENTIONAL) ESTIMATED AVAILABILITY WITHOUT REGARDING COST FOR EXPLOITATION
COAL	3.4 BILL. tCE	1,000 BILL. tCE	6,000 BILL. tCE
OIL	3.6 BILL. tOE	130 BILL. tOE	650 BILL. tOE
NATURAL GAS	2.5 TRILL. Nm ³	165 TRILL. Nm ³	500 TRILL. Nm ³
METHANE HYDRATES	-	-	1,500 TRILL. Nm ³ R & D*
TOTAL	8.0 BILL. tOE	967 BILL. tOE	21,000 BILL. tOE

Table 2: Fossil Fuels

* Presently some countries (e.g. U. S. A., India, Japan) investigate

[G. Bohrmann, R. Matsumoto, K. Sain]

- . the resources of methane hydrates especially in the sediments of continental sea shelves
- . a possible exploitation of these resources
- . the danger of release of methane from these resources into the atmosphere.

III-3 Summaries of R & D on energy technology reports from experts

3.1 Fossil fuels

The main efforts of R & D will be shortly described in the next few pages: they are concerned with:

- fossil fuel fired power plants (3.1.1)
(affecting 40 percent of fossil fuel consumption at present) to increase efficiency of producing electric power and to sequester and deposit carbon dioxide
[expert: Olaf Bolland, Norway]

- fossil fuel fired high temperature fuel cells (3.1.2)
[experts: H. Yokakawa, K. Tanimoto, Japan]

- liquid fossil fuels in transportation sector (3.1.3)
(affecting 24 percent of fossil fuel consumption at present) here conversion of natural gas to methanol)

- non conventional resources (3.1.4)
methane hydrates in sediments of continental sea shelves:
Concerning the risk of release of large amounts of methane into the atmosphere amplifying global warming
[expert: G. Bohrmann, Germany]
Concerning a possible exploitation of these resources
[experts: K. Sain, India, and R. Matsumoto, Japan]

3.1.1. Fossil fuel fired power plants including CO₂ sequestration and storage

(O. Bolland, Norway – see Annex AI-1)

Further development of the technologies of fossil fuel fired steam and gas turbine power plants especially to work at higher steam and gas inlet temperatures(mainly by designing and producing new materials) is expected to increase efficiency of converting high temperature heat to electric power significantly (by about 5 to 10 percent points).

But implementation of CO₂ sequestration partially via innovative methods, like membrane technologies, leads to a reduction of the overall conversion efficiency of the power plant

- via post combustion CO₂ sequestration by about 9 percent
- via pre combustion CO₂ sequestration by about 7 percent
- via oxy fuel combustion CO₂ sequestration by about 14 percent.

Table 3 summarizes expected development of the efficiency of fossil fuel fired power plants
[O. Bolland, COOR]:

3.1.3. Liquid fuels in the transportation sector: conversion of natural gas to methanol and liquefaction of coal to gasoline)

(S. Richter and U. Wagner, Germany – Annex AIV-2)

At present about 24 percent of fossil fuels are consumed for propulsion in the transportation sector. The technologies to convert natural gas to methanol and to liquefy coal to methanol and/or gasoline are available. In future -when cars with fuel cell electric motors may become available (see section 3.5) one might consider providing hydrogen (see section 3.4) for driving fuel cells from the fossil fuels with sequestration of CO₂ and its deposition

3.1.4. Non conventional resources of fossil fuels: methane hydrates in sediments of continental sea shelves

(G. Bohrmann, Germany – Annex AI-3; R. Matsumoto, Japan – Annex AI-5; , K. Sain, India-AnnexAI-4)

The amount of methane hydrates, especially in the sediments on the sea floor of continental sea shelves, has been estimated to about 1,500 trillion Nm³, corresponding to 12,000 billion tOE, about twice as much as the total conventional and non conventional resources of coal, oil and natural gas.

Concerning the possible release of methane from these sediments in the atmosphere

(G. Bohrmann- Annex AI-3):

The stability of these gas hydrate sediment deposits is only given within a narrow band of temperature and water pressure at the sea floor. Small changes of temperature and pressure can lead to a destabilization of these sediments and to corresponding release of methane finally into the atmosphere. As methane is a very climate sensitive gas such a release could increase greenhouse warming on earth significantly.

Concerning the exploration of methane hydrates and R & D towards commercial exploitation

(K. Sain, India, R. Matsumoto, Japan):

Exploration of marine gas hydrates are pursued via seismic survey, offshore exploration drilling and geochemical investigations. Different methods towards a possible economically viable mining like e.g. local depressurization and inhibitor injection are pursued together with proper hazard assessment.

3.2 Nuclear fission energy

At present about 16 percent of the global demand for electric power are met via nuclear fission power plants in 30 countries, with nuclear power plants providing from a few to about 80 percent of the local demand for electric power.

All relevant technologies for allowing a fairly economical use of nuclear fission energy, in an environmentally safe way are available, at least in principle. This holds for the whole chain of processes, from mining uranium deposits, operating nuclear power plants inherently safe with respect to the nuclear fission chain reaction as well as to the removal of the after-heat from radioactive decays after the stop of the nuclear chain reaction without any risk of a large accident (High Temperature Reactor, HTR), to finally the safe deposition of radioactive waste.

At present R & D on evolutionary improvements of nuclear power plants (NPP) to be built within the next decades (generation III NPP) are underway

- to further decrease the risk of large accidents of Light Water Reactors (LWR). The main activities are in USA, France and Japan.
- to avoid the risk of a large accident totally with HTR, inherently safe in any respect by physical principles (main activities in China, South Africa, USA, and Russia, Japan)

Furthermore R & D on revolutionary improvements of NPP to become available after many decades of further development (generation IV NPP) are studied at present, to finally develop most suitable technologies to allow provision of nuclear fission energy by very large amounts and this over a time period of at least many hundred years heading for nearly closed fuel cycle via breeding and reprocessing of fuels and heading for reducing the amount of high level radioactive waste largely either by burning all actinides in proper NPP or by transmutation of minor actinides to shorten the lifetime of radioactive waste:

- Very High Temperature Reactors (VHTR) with special emphasis on provision of hydrogen by thermo chemical catalytic water splitting
- Supercritical Water cooled Reactors (SWR)
- Lead and Sodium cooled Fast neutron Reactors with breeding potential, (LFR and SFR) heading finally for nearly closed fuel cycle
- Gas cooled Fast Reactors (GFR) and Molten Salt Reactors, (MSR), including burning of actinides from radioactive waste possible with Accelerator Driven Systems (ADS)
- Transmutation of minor actinides from high level radioactive waste either by bombardment with neutrons from a nuclear reactor or from a particle accelerator or e.g. by photo transmutation via laser driven high brightness gamma ray beams [LED].
- Thorium fuelled advanced Heavy Water Reactor, (ThHWR), and possibly other reactor types as well are studied in India (*K. Anantheraman and R.K. Sinha – AnnexA II-4*).

(These investigations are mainly pursued in an international cooperation within the Generation IV International Forum of -at present - 10 countries: USA, France, Japan, South Africa, UK, Canada, South Korea, Argentina, Brazil and Switzerland, and furthermore EURATOM. Further countries like e.g. China and India exhibit high interest in these developments.)

(*A. C. Kadak, USA – Annex AII-1. N. E. Todreas, USA – Annex A-II-3. M. Igashira, Japan – Annex AII-2*)

Furthermore, to enlarge the availability of uranium fuel (from at present some 100 years to possibly many 1000 years) an economic way to extract uranium from sea water is investigated in Japan. (*N. Seko and M. Tamada, Japan – Annex AII-5*).

The main challenge in all the further development of nuclear fission power technologies is to achieve solutions both technically and economically highly attractive, and this in environmentally safe ways.

3.3 Renewable energy

Before industrialization, renewable energy had been the only source of energy available:

- firewood to provide heat
- biomass for food, for horses and other animals for hauling transportation vehicles
- wind for propulsion of sailing boats
- wind and water power to run mills.

The onset of industrialization caused an extraordinarily fast rise of the demand on energy, caused a severe shortage of firewood in many countries. Fossil fuels soon became the dominant source of primary energy. The abundant and steady availability of fossil fuels and especially their low cost satisfied the newly arising additional demand on energy to provide any required fast rising amount of

- heat
- electric power
- fuels for propulsion in the transportation sector.

At present renewable energy can be used to provide only a rather limited amount of secondary energy, as indicated in Table 4.

	Via	Percentage of global demand	
Electric energy	Hydro power	18	} 20 %
	Wind power	0.3	
	Biomass	1	
	Geothermal	0.3	
	Sunlight	0.02	
Fuels Transportation sector	Ethanol	About 1	} 2 %
	Biodiesel	About 1	
Heat mainly for cooking in developing countries	Burning-non commercial- biomass (mainly firewood)	About 7% of the total global demand on primary energy	

Table 4: Amount of secondary energy provided by renewable energy

A more extended use of renewable energy at present is mainly handicapped

- by restricted availability (e.g. hydro power, biomass)
- by strongly fluctuating and intermittent availability of hydro river and wind power and of sunlight (see fig. 1) [STRO, WAG, GOE])
- by comparatively high investment cost and cost of energy provided (e.g. sunlight, geothermal energy).

Hydro River Power (typ. facility in Germany)

Wind Power (typ. facility at the German shore to the North Sea)

Sunlight Conversion via Photovoltaics (Freiburg, Germany)

Figure 1 - Availability of Electric Power from River Hydro [STRO], Wind [WAG] and Photovoltaic [GOE] Powerplants: Restrictions and Fluctuations in Time.

This is a challenge for R & D, making best use

- of interdisciplinary science and technology
- of nano sciences and nano technologies for design and production of new materials to achieve economically attractive solutions, as indicated in the following survey of reports from scientific experts.

3.3.1. "Solar" electric energy via photovoltaics (PV)

(A. Luque, Spain – Annex III-1)

Further R & D on PV is pursued

- on well established roads of mainly Si and furthermore Cu₂S, Cu(InGa) Se₂, CdTe technologies
- on completely new paths, including organic solar cells, to achieve much higher efficiencies and this at much lower cost
- on installing PV power systems in space in geostationary orbit - by innovative, sufficiently low cost space shuttle technologies -, thus to allow continuous provision of electric power, being transmitted to earth via microwaves directed onto ground based receiver antennas.

(H. Matsumoto and N. Shinohara, Japan – Annex AIII-3)

3.3.2. Storage of electric energy

(J. Ahearne, USA – Annex AIII-2)

Intimately connected to solar electric energy via PV on earth is the required storage of electric energy

- either directly in rechargeable batteries hoping to finally achieve much higher storage densities and this at much lower cost than at present
- or indirectly e.g. via producing and storing hydrogen (chapter 3.4) to be later used in fuel cells (chapter 3.5) to produce electric energy

Energy storage technologies - at present commercially available - are mainly Pumped Hydro Storage (globally 56 units with a total power of about 140 GW, corresponding to about 4 percent of the total installed power) and furthermore underground Compressed Air Energy Storage (2 units with a total power of 0.4 GW). These large scale energy storage technologies are most suitable for daily partially balancing the supply of electric power during the hours of high and of low demand.

3.3.3. Solar thermal power plants, STPP

(M. Romero, Spain – Annex A-III-4)

In solar thermal power plants - to be positioned in low latitude arid desert regions with high insolation - sunlight is concentrated via large area mirrors and converted to high temperature heat (of hot air or hot vapor) to then drive gas or steam turbines to produce electric power. With forthcoming possibilities of cheap storage of high temperature heat e.g. in sand STPP could provide electric power continuously, in plant units of up to about some 100 MWe

A further option of STPP, the Solar Chimney PP, is based on the idea of heating the air inside a largely extended greenhouse and letting escape the hot air through a high chimney in the

center of the greenhouse. Inside the chimney the upward draft drives a wind rotor generator. At present, a 200 MWe demonstration plant with a circular greenhouse of 7 km diameter and a chimney of 1 km height, is planned to be built near Mildura, Australia [BER].

3.3.4. *Wind power plants*

(H.-J. Wagner, R. Tryfonidou, Germany – Annex A-III-6)

The technology of wind rotor generator plants with up to a few MW max. electric power is well advanced. Major further R & D is concentrated on the development of wind rotor generator units with some MW max. electric power to be installed “offshore” in shallow ocean regions to extend the intervals of providing electric power from typically up to about 20 percent of availability in time - typical for on shore and inland wind rotor installations - to about 30 to 40 percent.

3.3.5. *Hydro Power*

Concerning Hydro Power

- the technologies of high pressure reservoir and low pressure river power plants are well established [PUER, STRO, YUAN]
- the technology of tidal power plants is available in principle and has been investigated comprehensively [WAL]. But its further realization, beyond the existing 240 MW tidal power plant at the Rance estuary in France, has been barred mainly by the rather high expenses to be expected.
- the technologies of ocean wave and ocean current power conversion still require extensive R & D both for large power facilities to be installed in the open ocean as well as for small power facilities to be installed in shallow coastal areas.

3.3.6. *Biofuels*

(R. C. Cerqueira Leite, Brazil – Annex AIII-5)

For providing ethanol from sugar cane in Brazil an energy efficiency ratio, - the ratio of the caloric energy of the biofuel to the total commercial energy input for growing biomass and its conversion to biofuel - of about 8 has been obtained. For producing ethanol, methanol or biodiesel from other kinds of biomass the energy efficiency ratio obtained so far is much lower. Providing biofuel from biomass may be rather promising for countries with proper large areas of land suitable for agricultural energy crops at present like e.g. Brazil. On a global scale the bottle neck for providing a large fraction of the demand on liquid fuels for the transportation sector is the limited availability of sufficient areas for agricultural land to provide sufficient amounts of food for a world population, expected to rise from about 6 to at least about 9 billion humans.

To further enlarge the total area of agricultural land by a significant amount extensive R & D is required towards re-cultivation of sufficiently large areas of arid land including the provision of water for artificial irrigation by desalination and purification - this at sufficiently low cost -, this artificial irrigation at least for some time, till the re-cultivation to green land may change the local climate to obtain sufficient natural precipitation.

3.3.7. Geothermal energy

The use of the rather limited resources of geothermal energy from natural hot water and vapour wells as well as the withdrawal of hot water from deep aquifer layers via artificial bore holes is established. Rather limited R & D is pursued to withdraw heat from deep hot dry respectively wet rock layers - e.g. in Soultz-sous-Forêts in France - via drilling boreholes into 3 to 5 km depth, impressing water through one of the boreholes and to withdraw vapor at temperatures of 120 to 200 degrees Celsius through a second borehole [CLA].

3.4 Hydrogen

(W. E. Evenson, USA – Annex AIV-1; S. Richter and U. Wagner, Germany- Annex AIV-2; K. Onuki and M. Ogawa, Japan – Annex AIV-3; J. Samseth, Norway – AnnexAIV-4. C. Beckervordersandforth, Germany – Annex AIV-5)

Hydrogen is a secondary energy carrier to possibly be provided from any type of primary energy respectively of secondary energy like electric energy or high temperature heat. At present about 50 million t hydrogen/anno (with a caloric value corresponding to 140 million tOE or about 10 percent of the present demand on liquid fuels in the transportation sector) are produced globally from natural gas. The provision of hydrogen in the chain electrolysis, liquefaction, storage and distribution requires the expenditure of at least 2 kWh electric energy for 1 kWh caloric energy of hydrogen provided. Therefore a provision of large amounts of hydrogen via electrolysis would require a corresponding large rise of the demand on electric energy.

For future provision of hydrogen by large amounts rather challenging R & D along different new ways is required and is partially already going on, e.g.

- photo electrolysis (by special PV cells)
- solar thermal \
- photo chemical - catalytic
- photo biological - water splitting
- thermo chemical /

To provide hydrogen as an innovative fuel in the transportation sector to a large scale economic solutions for stationary and mobile storage, handling, transportation and distribution have yet to be found.

As an alternative to the difficult handling of hydrogen, R & D towards converting hydrogen directly at the location of its production via synthesis with CO₂ extracted from the atmosphere to a proper synfuel like e.g. methanol may finally lead to avoid the expensive infrastructure of a future hydrogen economy [LACK].

3.5 Low temperature fuel cells

(C. Cremers and U. Stimming, Germany – Annex AV-1)

Low temperature fuel cells, especially Polymer Electrolyte Membrane Fuel Cells, PEMFC, and Direct Methanol Fuel Cells, DMFC, are regarded as forthcoming future technologies for mobile provision of electric power especially on board of fuel cell electric motor vehicles.

Further challenging, rather imaginative R & D is required to overcome the many difficulties at present, especially

- to improve membrane materials for higher operation temperatures
- to improve the catalyst structures
- to increase conversion efficiency
- to achieve higher power density
- to improve systems designs
- to enlarge choice of useable fuels
- to take into consideration bio-electrochemical fuel cells
- and last not least to reduce the cost of fuel cells by up to two orders of magnitude to become competitive with present vehicle propulsion by internal combustion engines.

3.6 Nuclear fusion energy

(R. Fonck, USA – Annex AVI-1; P. K. Kaw, India – Annex AIV-2; C. Hidalgo, Spain – Annex AIV-3; B. Richter, USA – Annex AIV-5; K. Mima, Japan – Annex AIV-4)

Concerning the possible use of *nuclear fusion energy* by means of nuclear fusion power plants, up till now only fusion processes in principle, rather limited in power and in operation time, have been achieved so far.

Further necessary steps of the technology development of nuclear fusion power plants are

- to achieve the necessary high fusion power over sufficient long operation time
- to develop proper materials with sufficient stability for the first wall of the fusion vessel
- to extract the rather high thermal power from the walls of the fusion vessel
- to breed the necessary tritium fuel for fusion by neutron lithium interactions inside the walls of the fusion vessel and to extract it
- finally to prove the technology of a nuclear fusion power plant to be sufficiently economic.

To achieve the required goals, rather different options of fusion technologies are pursued at present:

- magnetic confinement of the hot fusion plasma, initially heated up with HF and neutral atom beams (TOKAMAK : ITER, STELLARATOR)
- inertial confinement of the fusion plasma initially heated up with lasers and laser generated x-rays, with “z-pinch” electric pulse generated x-rays, with heavy ion beams.

And there may be further options initiating fusion to become available like e.g. muon catalytic fusion including the recovery of muons sticking to helium nuclei produced by fusion of deuteron and tritium nuclei [NAG] or initiating the heating of a fusion plasma via standing acoustic waves leading to strong compression shock waves [TAL].

To achieve the goals via any of these options, at least 2 to 3 further successive steps of R & D are required, mainly at test facilities and demonstration plants. Each step is rather expensive in manpower and cost and will require a time span of 1 to 2 decades for construction and operation. The high expenditures call for international collaborations to pursue these options.

The option, most advanced at present, is Magnetic Confinement Fusion with a Tokamak device: The International Thermonuclear Experimental Reactor, ITER, is the next step along

this line and is being planned by an international collaboration of scientists and engineers from the European Union, Japan, Russia, USA, China and South Korea.

Hopefully all possible promising options of fusion technologies will be pursued until at least one of them has led to a viable technical as well as economical solution.

IV-CONCLUSIONS – OUTLOOK

It is an important and exciting task of physics concerning R & D on energy technologies, to discover and prepare new ways based on brilliant ideas, making use of computational physics, nano sciences and nano technologies to provide any secondary energy demanded from any kind of primary energy

- in sufficient amount
- in an environmentally safe way, especially
 - . on one hand to fight climate change and to limit respectively to avoid the threatening high cost of damages by climate change
 - . on the other hand to reduce respectively to avoid the risk of large accidents at nuclear power plants
- at sufficient low cost

meeting the still rising demand on energy mainly caused by economically fast developing countries where the restricted availability of energy is a limiting factor for further development.

A large variety of energy technologies can be tackled by challenging R & D covering nearly any branch of modern physics but also chemistry and material science, never restricted to one branch alone, always basic physics and applied physics linked together inseparably.

R & D of some of these technologies may require investments of only some 100 human years (like possibly innovative photovoltaics and battery storage). Others may require investments of some 100,000 human years (like fusion power and photovoltaics power in space). Nevertheless all of these technologies have to be investigated further.

There is high interest in any of the innovative energy technologies in many countries around the globe including OECD countries as well as especially countries with high and fast rising populations like e.g. China, India, Brazil. (These 3 countries together –representing at present 40 percent of the world population- cause already nearly 20 percent of the global demand on energy and this share may well increase to about 50 percent within the forthcoming decades.)

Different countries put different emphasis on improving the use of the different sources of primary energy, fossil fuels, nuclear fission, renewable energy and nuclear fusion. But all countries look for appropriate scientific cooperation in R & D of energy technologies of their choice.

To be kept in mind: fossil fuels will continue to be the dominant source of primary energy at least within the next few decades. It will take some to many decades to improve the use of other sources of primary energy like e.g. nuclear fission and renewable energy to be able to play a much more important role to satisfy our demand on energy than nowadays. This is intimately linked to the ability to cut cost of providing energy from nuclear and especially from renewable energy appreciably, and concerning the increased use of renewable energy with strongly intermittent availability to find new ways to store energy -especially electric energy -efficiently and cost effectively. Nuclear fusion energy may become an option only in the far more distant future of many decades.

Therefore R & D on clean fossil fuel technologies with highest possible efficiencies and including CO₂ sequestration and storage respectively use is of utmost importance.

V- ANNEX A: LIST OF EXPERT REPORTS ON R & D OF SPECIAL ENERGY TECHNOLOGIES

I. Fossil Energy

AI-1. Power Generation with CO₂ Capture and Sequestration

Olaf Bolland, Norwegian University of Science and Technology, Trondheim, Norway

AI-2. Future needs for fundamental research in the oil and gas industry especially on non conventional resources

Jon Samseth, SINTEF, Norway

AI-3. Oceanic Hydrates, a dynamic reservoir of methane within the marine environment

Gerhard Bohrmann, Department of Geosciences, University of Bremen, Germany

AI-4. Methane Hydrates: Present Status of worldwide R & D on the utilisation of Gas Hydrates for Power Production

Kalachand Sain, National Geophysical Research Institute, Hyderabad, India

AI-5. Exploration of Marine Gas Hydrates around Japanese Islands

Ryo Matsumoto, Earth and Planetary Science, University of Tokyo, Japan

II. Nuclear Fission Energy

AII-1. New Nuclear Energy Plant Designs

Andrew C. Kadak, Professor of the Practice, MIT, Cambridge, US

AII-2. R & D Needs of Fission Energy Generation

Neil E. Todreas, MIT, Cambridge, US

AII-3. Physics Based R & D for Innovative Fission Reactors

Masayuki Igashira, Research Laboratory for Nuclear Reactors, Tokyo Institute of Technology, Japan

AII-4. Present Status of worldwide R & D on the Utilisation of Thorium for Power Production

K. Anantharaman and R. K. Sinha, Bhabha Atomic Research Center, Trombay, Mumbai, India

AII-5. R & D towards Recovery of Uranium from Sea Water

Noriaki Seko and Maseao Tamada, Takasaki RCRE, JAERI, Japan

III. Renewable Energy

AIII-1. R & D Needs in Photovoltaics

Antonio Luque, Universidad Politécnica, Madrid, Spain

AIII-2. Storage of (Electric) Energy:

-Batteries: Present and Future

-Pumped Hydro and Compressed Air Energy Storage

John Ahearne, Research Triangle Park, NC, US

AIII-3. Space Solar Power Systems: Development Status and Future Perspectives

Hiroshi Matsumoto and Naoki Shinohara, Research Institute of Sustainable Humanosphere, Kyoto University, Japan

AIII-4. Thermal Power Plants

Manuel Romero, CIEMAT, Madrid, Spain

AIII-5. Energy from Biomass

Rogério C. de Cerqueira Leite, Universidade Estadual De Campinas, Brazil

AIII-6. Wind Energy - Status and R & D Activities

Hermann-Josef Wagner and Rodoula Tryfonidou, LEE, Ruhr-Universität Bochum, Germany

IV. Hydrogen

AIV-1. The Potential for the Hydrogen Energy Economy

William E. Evenson, Brigham Young University, USA

AIV-2. R & D towards Provision of Hydrogen

Stefan Richter and Ulrich Wagner, Forschungsstelle für Energiewirtschaft und Technische Universität München, Germany

AIV-3. Report on the Thermochemical Water Splitting (via the Iodine Sulphur Cycle) at the HTTR

Kaoru Onuki and Masuro Ogawa, JAERI, Japan

AIV-4. Hydrogen Production and Storage

Jon Samseth, SINTEF, Norway

AIV-5. Use of Natural Gas Pipelines to Transport Hydrogen Gas

Christian P. Beckervordersandforth, Ruhrgas AG, Essen, Germany

V. Fuel Cells

AV-1. Low Temperature Fuel Cells: Development Status and Future Perspectives

Carsten Cremers and Ulrich Stimming, Bavarian Center of Applied Energy Research, TU Munich, Germany

AV-2. Solid Oxide Fuel Cells

Harumi Yokakawa, National Institute of Advanced Industrial Science and Technology, AIST, Japan

AV-3. Technolgical Status of Molten Carbonate Fuel Cell

K. Tanimoto, National Institute of Advanced Industrial Science and Technology, Japan

VI. Nuclear Fusion Energy

AVI-1. R & D Opportunities for Fusion Energy

Ray Fonck, University of Wisconsin, Madison, USA

AVI-2. Fusion Energy using TOKAMAKs

Predhiman K. Kaw, Institute for Plasma Research, Bhat, Gandhinagar, India

AVI-3. Physics Issues on Magnetically Confined Plasmas: Stellarator Devices

Carlos Hidalgo, EURATOM-CIEMAT, Madrid, Spain

AVI-4. Status Report on Inertial Energy Fusion

Burton Richter, Stanford University, USA

AVI-5. Report on Laser Fast Ignition for Inertial Fusion Energy

Kunioki Mima, Institute of Laser Engineering, Osaka University, Japan

VI-ANNEX B: LIST OF COUNTRY REPORTS ON THEIR SPECIAL ENERGY SITUATION

-P. R. China	Huo Yuping
-India	P. K. Kaw
-Brazil	R. C. Cerqueira Leite
-USA	J. F. Ahearne
-Germany	K. Heinloth
-Russia	O. N. Favorskyi
-Japan	Y. Nagai
-France	H. Nifenecker
-Southern European Countries (Italy, Spain and Portugal)	F. Yndurain
-Nordic European Countries (Iceland, Norway, Denmark, Sweden, Finland)	J. Samseth
-South Africa	T. Alfstad,

VII-REFERENCES (besides the reports from experts attached)

- BER M. A. dos S. Bernardes et. al, Thermal and technical analyses of solar chimneys, Solar Energy 75 (2003) 511 - 524
- BGR German Federal Agency for Geoscience and Natural Resources: Reserves, Resources and Availability of Energy Raw Materials, Hannover 1998
- BRO Brockhaus Encyclopaedia, Mannheim 1987
- CLA C. Clauser, Geothermal Energy, In HEI, Subvolume C
- COOR COORETEC: Research and Development Concept for Zero-Emission Fossil Fuelled Power Plants, Documentation Nr. 527, German Federal Ministry of Economics and Labour, Berlin 2003
- GOE A. Goetzberger, Photovoltaic Power Generation, in HEI, Subvolume C
- HEI K. Heinloth (Editor), Energy Technologies, Landolt-Börnstein, Group VIII, Volume 3, Subvolume A (Fossil Energy), 2003, Subvolume B (Nuclear Energy), 2004, Subvolume C (Renewable Energy, to be published 2005), Springer Publ. Co, Berlin 2003/2004/2005
- IEA World Energy Outlook 2002, CO₂ emissions from fuel combustion, 2003
- IPCC Intergovernmental Panel on Climate Change, 1st, 2nd and 3rd Assessment Report, Cambridge 1991, 1996, 2001
- LACK K. S. Lackner, Zero Emission Coal Alliance, ZECA, Columbia Univ., NY, USA, 2003
- LED K. W. D. Ledingham et al., Laserdriven photo-transmutation ..., J. Phys. D: Appl. Phys. 36 (2003) L 79 - 82
- NAG K. Nagamine, Muon Catalyzed Fusion in HEI, Subvolume B
- PUER E. Puerer and G. Gökler, Hydroelectric Reservoir Power Plants, in HEI, Subvolume C
- STRO T. Strobl and F. Zunic, Hydroelectric River Powerplants, in HEI, Subvolume C
- TAL R. P. Taleyarkhan et al., Science Vol. 295, p. 1868, March 2002 and 2004 Phys. Rev. E69, 036109
- WAG H.-J. Wagner, Windelectric Power, in HEI, Subvolume C
- WAL W. van Walsum and Won-Oh Song, Tidal Power Plants, in HEI, Subvolume C
- WEC World Energy Council, 2004
- YUAN Yuan Dafu, Tian Ziqin, Wang Shuqing, Mechanical and Electrical Design of the Three Gorges Project, in HEI, Subvolume C

Annex 1: Expert reports on R & D of special Energy Technologies

<http://pi.physik.uni-bonn.de/~heinloth/IUPAP/>

Annex 2: Country reports on their special energy situation

<http://pi.physik.uni-bonn.de/~heinloth/IUPAP/>

VIII-USEFUL ABBREVIATIONS AND DEFINITIONS

1-Energy Units

- Joule:J
- Btu=British thermal unit= $1,055.10^3$ J=1,055 kJ
- kWh= $3,600.10^6$ J=3,6 MJ, kWh_e=kWh electric, kWh_{th}=kWh thermal
- tOE=ton of oil equivalent= 42.10^9 J=42 GJ
- tCE=ton of coal equivalent= $29,3.10^9$ J=29,3 GJ
- MWh= $3,6.10^9$ J=3,6 GJ

2-Power Units

- Watt:W
- Btu/hour=Btu/h=0,29 W

3-Volume

- Nm³=10³ liter under normal conditions of pressure and temperature
- petroleum barrel= $1,59.10^{-1}$ m³
- bOE= barrel of oil equivalent

4-Symbols

- P=Peta= 10^{15}
- T=Tera= 10^{12}
- G=Giga= 10^9
- M=Mega= 10^6
- k=kilo= 10^3

5-Definitions

- Fuel Cell: a cell in which electricity is produced through the oxidation of a fuel (methanol,...).
- Natural and Enriched Uranium (U). Natural Uranium is made of 99,27 % of ²³⁸U, 0,72 % of ²³⁵U and 0,005 % of ²³⁴U: to be able to function , a reactor must have 3,5 to 4,4 % of ²³⁵U. This operation is called enrichment.
- NPP: Nuclear Power Plant: it is composed of:
 - . the fuel core : natural U, enriched UO₂, UO₂-PuO₂....).
 - . the moderator : it is a material that slows the velocity of neutrons so they may be absorbed by nuclei: ordinary water, heavy water, graphite....).
 - . the coolant: it can be a gas (CO₂ or He) or a liquid (light water-pressurized or boiling, heavy water-pressurized, sodium....).There are various types but most of the plants are light water reactors, using the steam cycle to generate electricity with pressurized or boiling water.
some examples: LWR (Light Water Reactor), BWR (Boiling Water Reactor), AWBR (Advanced Boiling Water Reactor), HTR (High Temperature Reactor),

VHTR (Very High Temperature Reactor), MSR (Molten Salt Reactor), SCWR (Supercritical Water Cooled Reactor), BREEDER (reactor designed to produce more fissionable fuel at faster rate than it consumes fuel for electricity production).

- Tokamak: toroidal device in which a gas of deuterium and tritium is heated to produce nuclear reactions of fusion of the nuclei. ITER is the next generation.
- Stellarator: high temperature plasma device with a racetrack shape
- Tritium: isotope of hydrogen with an atomic mass of 3.